

Physical Activity Through Sustainable Transport Approaches (PASTA)

D1.1 Description and classification of AM measures including factors affecting their effectiveness

Literature review and assessment of state-of-the-art of AM WP1

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List of abbreviations

AM	Active Mobility
AMM	Active Mobility Measure
PA	Physical Activity

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Executive summary

The PASTA project ran from October 2013-October 2017, and was about getting individuals to be more physically active by integrating physical activity (PA) into their daily transport activities through walking and cycling. This report reflects the work and findings from the first work package of the PASTA project. In a nutshell, this report looks at what active mobility (AM) is, what can be done to increase active mobility, and what factors affect active mobility.

The audience for this document is twofold: first this document is for the PASTA consortium to communicate findings of relevance to other work done during the project; secondly, the audience for this document are individuals who are interested in finding out about what active mobility is, what measures exist to increase active mobility, and what factors could affect levels of active mobility. This second audience covers those from health, transport and related fields, as well as different sectors, since it includes a review of scientific literature delivered in a non-scientific report.

The overall methodology used to answer the research questions comprised of a literature review, expert input and complementary searches to cover gaps.

The review of the literature and discussion with experts shows that many terms are used for active mobility. Within certain countries and contexts, certain terms are favoured, and all terms are found to have ambiguities of some kind. There is no obvious choice, but based on the findings we would recommend to use the term “active mobility”. This term is commonly used within the EU context, and favoured in the PASTA stakeholder meeting in Brussels in April 2014. “Active mobility” should be used in the PASTA project.

For the PASTA project, this definition of active mobility is used: “Active mobility is regular physical activity undertaken as a means of transport. It includes travel by foot, bicycle and other vehicles which require physical effort to get moving. Use of public transport is also included in the definition as it often involves some walking or cycling as access and egress points. It does not include walking, cycling or other physical activity that is undertaken for recreation.”

To get to a common understanding of terminology in the project, a glossary was set up on the shared PASTA drive. This document was free for any members of the consortium to update or comment. The glossary of these terms and definitions can be found in Annex to this report.

Part of the work in this work package was to classify active mobility measures (actions undertaken in order to increase the level of active mobility) to make sure we have a good understanding of what AM measures are, and to communicate internally and externally about AM measures. Classes for active mobility measures have been defined as strategic policy measures, social environment measures, physical environment/infrastructure measures and regulation and legislation measures. A list of measures collected in the literature review is included in an Annex to this report.

A central tenet of the PASTA project was that increasing levels of active mobility is a positive thing that will bring benefit to European society. At the basis of this is an understanding of

what we know about what affects levels of active mobility. Factors that affect active mobility include determinants and correlates of active mobility. They give us information on what factors can affect the success of AM measures, and which factors affect the implementation of AM measures. The collection of factors affecting AM is structured along the following categories; policies, physical environment, safety related factors, social environment and individual factors.

A policy represents a decision made by an individual or group which aims to achieve a specific aim or aims. In summary, there is very little known about the effectiveness of policy measures in increasing levels of active mobility, although the little that is known seems to indicate that comprehensive approaches would seem to be more effective than individual measures.

Factors in the physical environment include transport options, the built environment and natural environment. There are a number of physical environment factors that affect the levels of active mobility including the existence and quality of walking and cycling infrastructure, weather, and topographical features. There needs to be a stronger focus on determinants research with improved causal inference rather than repetition of cross-sectional correlates studies.

Safety related factors are important in the determination of which mode of transport a person chooses. Safety relates both to 'objective' safety (i.e. a measurable number of incidents, injuries, fatalities, etc) and 'subjective' safety which is the perceived safety of individuals. There are a number of factors that affect objective safety for active modes including infrastructure, traffic conditions, driver behaviour. Perceived safety is affected by numerous factors; from social factors (e.g. public acceptance/opinion) to infrastructure (level of well-lit, accessible, segregated infrastructure). The relationships are often non-linear and there are complexities arising between objective and subjective safety and levels of active mobility.

The social environment plays an important role in determining whether individuals will partake in active mobility. Whether an individual cycles or not depends on how they perceive cycling, and this depends on the prevailing social norms, their social support network and whether active mobility is "normal". Social norms can be subjective (what others think about how an individual should behave) or descriptive (what the individual thinks is normal). Both affect how an individual can perceive active mobility, and whether they engage in it. Promoters of active mobility can work on altering the social environment in order to increase levels of active mobility.

Individual factors include socio-economic status, household composition, car ownership, etc. They also include factors relating to personal attributes and beliefs such as habit or stages of change. There is evidence that active mobility is associated with individual factors such as gender, age, physical ability, level of education, household income, household structure (and presence of children), vehicle access (both car and non-motorised modes), driver's licence status, ethnicity, working situation and an active lifestyle. Prior behaviour, habits and life events are also individual factors affecting AM.

In summary, there are many factors that affect levels of active mobility, and the relationship between factors is complex. Although we have tried to group factors into different categories, it is clear than when we delve into more detail that it is seldom possible to isolate individual

factors and how they affect levels of active mobility as the factors are inter-linked. Successful AM measures should focus on several different strands: the individual, social environment, physical environment and policy. This has further been taken up in the PASTA conceptual framework of active mobility behaviour. A rapid review of the literature shows that successful measures to increase active mobility must focus on all of these aspects, and at the same be implemented in broad schemes – “a multi-pronged approach”.

1. Introduction

The PASTA project was about getting individuals to be more physically active by integrating physical activity (PA) into their daily transport activities through walking and cycling. This report reflects the work and findings from the first work package of the PASTA project. In a nutshell, this report looks at what active mobility (AM) is, what can be done to increase active mobility, and what factors affect active mobility.

1.1. Background

PASTA stands for “Physical Activity Through Sustainable Transport Approaches”. Increasing physical activity is one of the key approaches to address non-communicable diseases. Yet, only one third of the European population is estimated to meet the minimum recommended levels of physical activity, which for adults correspond to at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity throughout the week (WHO, 2010).

In the face of myriad challenges, increasing PA through traditional approaches such as public health advocacy, sports and leisure time physical activity alone, would not be sufficient. Integrating PA into daily life through routine behaviour is key. Yet for too long, the focus of such efforts has been limited to advising individuals, with little consideration of the role of social and physical environments (Das, 2012; Sallis, 2009). Empowering individuals to engage in active life styles requires empowering policy makers, health professionals and planners with the knowledge and tools to create the environments in which individuals can easily take up healthy behaviours.

Active mobility, namely walking, cycling and the use of public transport, is well suited to provide routine activity, e.g. for commuting, visiting friends or family, running errands, etc. As such, AM can contribute considerably to total physical activity and result in significant positive health effects. Active commuting is associated with higher general physical activity levels and lower body weight in adults (Wanner et al., 2012). It is also associated with approximately 30 % of reduced risk of mortality for all causes (Andersen et al., 2000). Those who engage in active mobility on a regular basis seem to exceed the WHO recommendations for physical activity, e.g. in Switzerland by as much as double (approx. 60 min per day). Furthermore, active mobility is practicable for most individuals. In contrast to sports or exercise, AM requires less time and motivation, since it provides both convenience as a mode of transport and exercise, and is economically affordable for most people, providing an equitably accessible form of PA. As such, it has the potential to reach parts of the population, which are not receptive to appeals and benefits of sports and exercise, or cannot afford them.

Current urban mobility patterns in Europe provide ample potential to increase AM. Mobility patterns are often dominated by car use, and there is ample room to switch trips to walking, cycling and public transport, although the potential for switching existing car trips to active mobility is not as large (Beckx et al., 2013). Large parts of the European population do not use AM on a regular basis, although there are some obvious exceptions (e.g. in Copenhagen or Amsterdam close to half of all trips are by bicycle and in several Swiss cities, more than

half are by walking).

The notion that high levels of active mobility are not a given, but rather a result of numerous factors including effective measures and policies to create safe and enabling environments for active mobility along with promoting policies, among other factors, is becoming more apparent in research and practice.

The work reported here is about creating a common understanding at the basis of the PASTA project, both for the project team to communicate with each other, and when communicating about the project externally. Although this could seem like a somewhat trivial task, it is important to note that the field of active mobility is highly interdisciplinary one. Those working in active mobility are from different disciplines (e.g. health, transport and epidemiology) and different sectors (academic, private and public administration), and to work together means being able to communicate with each other. This is true in the field of active mobility as a whole, but also within the PASTA consortium. It was important that the project started with a common understanding. This common understanding came through an analysis of definitions and terminology, and existing literature dealing with active mobility.

1.2. Who is this document for?

The audience for this document is twofold: first this document is for the PASTA consortium to communicate findings of relevance to other work done during the project¹; secondly, the audience for this document are individuals who are interested in finding out about active mobility: what it is, what measures exist to increase active mobility, and what factors could affect levels of active mobility. This second audience covers those from health, transport and related fields, as well as different sectors, since it includes a review of scientific literature delivered in a non-scientific report.

1.3. Aims and research questions

Aims

There are three aims of this report:

- In order to use distinct and consistent terms within the PASTA project, a first central aim of this report is to *comprehensively define what is meant by the terms “active mobility” and “active mobility measures”*.
- Secondly, this report will help in *identifying types of measures* that will be studied in later work packages and which will be included in a good practice guide. This aim also includes a *classification of identified measures* including details of evaluation.
- A third aim is to *identify factors affecting implementation of active mobility measures as well as an increase in active mobility*. The identification of such factors is crucial in providing guidance to people implementing active mobility measures in the future.

¹ A first draft of this report was available and circulated in summer 2014

Research questions

There are several research questions answered in this report:

- What is active mobility, and what is an active mobility measure? What are the synonyms used for these terms?
- What are examples of different types of active mobility measures?
- What is a 'good practice' or 'successful' active mobility measure? What is a 'comprehensive programme' for active mobility in a city? How can active mobility measures be evaluated?
- Which are the known factors (including beyond transport) related to the successful implementation of an active mobility intervention? What are the known factors related to the success of an active mobility measure in increasing the level of active mobility through active mobility measures? What are the correlates and determinants of active mobility? What are the different categories of factors?
- What are the relationships between factors related to active mobility?

2. Methodology

The overall methodology used to answer the research questions comprised of three elements:

- Literature review
- Expert input
- Complementary searches to cover gaps

This overall framework was used, but adapted to the different research questions to be answered. This is described in more detail below.

2.1. Research question: definitions of active mobility

This section applies to the following questions:

Research questions	How was the research question answered?
What is active mobility, and what is an active mobility measure?	Literature review, check result with external experts
What are the synonyms used for these terms?	
What misconceptions arise with the use of terms across different fields and cultural barriers in Europe?	
What are examples of different types of active mobility measures?	

Literature review

To perform the literature review, we followed the Rapid Evidence Assessment (REA) methodology. The objective of the REA is to provide a balanced assessment of existing knowledge within a narrow time span by using systematic review methods but make concessions to the breadth or depth of the study by applying strict delimitations. For more information on the REA methodology, see the description provided by the Civil Service, UK².

The search strings were defined explicitly, and the sources that the partners would search in were also defined in collaboration with partners (see Annex – practical instructions for searches).

In the literature search, 304 scientific articles were recorded (after removal of duplicates). The results were sorted by discipline based on journal name and title of article, resulting in the following figures:

- Public health: 160 articles
- Transport: 120 articles
- Other disciplines: 24 articles

Aside from scientific articles, also “grey literature” was reviewed, mainly European Union websites related to research and practice regarding sustainable transport.

Expert input

On April 7th 2014, a PASTA workshop was held in Brussels. The aim of the workshop was to ensure that the terms and definitions found in the literature review were applicable amongst stakeholders/potential in different fields. A second aim was to identify terms, definitions and factors that are used by stakeholders/potential users and that were not found in the literature review.

The workshop was organised jointly with WP5 leader, Polis and jointly with two other relevant events to attract more participants: Stepping Stones Workshop and Polis Environment & Health Working Group meeting. Representatives from the PASTA case study cities were invited. The majority of the participants belonged to the transport discipline (77 %), while 23 % belonged to the health discipline. About 50 % of the participants worked within the policy sector, 19 % in research, 12 % in the planning sector and 19 % worked within other sectors.

Expert input was provided by associates of the PASTA consortium and PASTA advisory board at the Stockholm consortium meeting held on April 24-25th 2014. Participants discussed in small groups about the findings from the literature search and the expert workshop, and gave feedback on the terms. Decisions on which terms to use and their

² <http://www.civilservice.gov.uk/networks/gsr/resources-and-guidance/rapid-evidence-assessment>

definitions were made in this meeting.

Complementary Searches to cover gaps

Upon completing the literature search, and presenting it, some gaps were identified. This largely consisted of European Commission sites, and terms used in previous European projects. This was deemed important since PASTA is a European project, and terminology should take the European dimension into consideration.

A complementary search was made in the Eltis (European local transport information service) Case Study database, an Urban Mobility Portal managed by the European Commission. The case study database is practitioner orientated, covering a broad range of European countries.

Not a quantitative analysis

The aim of this work was to provide the PASTA project with suggestions on which vocabulary to use, and this naturally relies on subjective decisions. The aim of this work was not to make a quantitative analysis of which terms are used in which contexts.

The data collected cannot be used for quantitative analysis. Given the limited timeframe for the task, searches, screenings and recording of results differ between the contributing parties. Some data sources, research fields, sectors, terms and definitions are over-represented in the results. This is however, not contrary to the aims of the work, since we sought out different sources to cover the sources of interest to the project.

2.2. Research question: glossary

This section applies to the following questions:

Research questions	How was research question answered?
What is a 'good practice' or 'successful' active transport measure? What is a 'comprehensive programme' for active transport in a city? How can active transport measures be evaluated?	Collection of terms in glossary defined by consortium

Expert input through joint development of glossary

To define these terms in the PASTA project, a glossary of common terms of relevance to PASTA was set up. This glossary was a joint effort of the PASTA consortium, and all partners were encouraged to make changes on several occasions. The glossary was available to all project partners on Google Drive throughout the project, and was constantly reviewed and updated.

Terms which were deemed especially important were presented at the Stockholm consortium meeting (24th-25th April 2014 in Stockholm), where feedback was requested. These terms were the following:

- Good practice active mobility measure
- Successful active mobility measure
- Innovative active mobility measure

2.3. Research questions: factors

This section applies to the following questions

Research questions	How was research question answered?
Which are the known factors (including beyond transport) related to the successful implementation of an active transport intervention? What are the known factors related to the success of an active transport measure in increasing the level of active transport through active transport measures? What are the correlates and determinants of active transport? What are the different categories of factors?	Literature review in scientific literature
What are the relationships between factors?	Expert input, discussion consortium

A literature review was performed by the partners based on categories of factors from the PASTA framework. The literature review was based on the same REA methodology as described above.

3. What is active mobility

3.1. Our definition

In the PASTA project, active mobility is:

Active mobility is regular physical activity undertaken as a means of transport. It includes travel by foot, bicycle and other vehicles which require physical effort to get moving. Use of public transport is also included in the definition as it often involves some walking or cycling to pick-up and from drop-off points. It does not include walking, cycling or other physical activity that is undertaken for recreation.

3.2. Which terms and definitions are used?

Four terms are mainly used to describe AM:

- Active mobility
- Active travel
- Active transport
- Active transportation

Other terms are used, but not as often. The main findings regarding these four terms are presented here.

3.2.1. Active mobility

The findings on the use of this term are as follows:

Active mobility is rarely used in the scientific literature

According to the literature searches performed in the scientific literature, this term is very rarely used (see Figure 1). But all examples were very recent indicating it may be a new term in this field.

Figure 1 Terms used in screened academic literature.

In European policy and projects, this is a commonly used term

The expert workshop in Brussels showed that “active mobility” was a favoured term to use, both in terms of individual preferences, and after group discussions, it was preferred by about 50% of attendees. This was complemented and in line with findings from the search of terms used in Eltis case studies where active travel and active mobility were the most common used terms (see Figure 3). Additionally, it was pointed out during the PASTA consortium meeting in Brussels that “active mobility” is the term used by the THE PEP³ in strategic documents and activities.

Active mobility is preferred by several (non-english speaking) European countries

Discussion with the PASTA consortium at a workshop on 24th April 2014 in Stockholm revealed that “active mobility” was a direct translation of the term used in several other European languages (e.g. German, Dutch and Spanish).

3.2.2. Active travel

Active travel is (almost) standard in the UK / Ireland

Both from the scientific literature and other sources identified, when identified by country, ‘active travel’ is clearly the predominant term in the UK and in Ireland (although there are far fewer examples from Ireland) (see Figures 2 and 3).

³ Transport, Health and Environment Pan-European Programme: www.unece.org/thepep

Figure 2 Terms used in academic literature, sorted by region.

Figure 3 Terms used in ELTIS case studies, sorted by region.

When we look at the results from the scientific literature, we see that “active travel” is becoming more common over time.

3.2.3. Active Transport

Most commonly used term in Europe (non UK) in scientific literature

In the scientific literature, the term active transport dominates in Europe (see Figures 2 and 4).

Looking at the date that articles were published, it seems however that this term is becoming less common over time.

Is a term favoured in the transport field, but not in the public health field

In the scientific literature, it seems that this term is more likely to appear in the transport field than in the public health field (see Figure).

Figure 4 Terms used in academic literature, sorted by discipline.

3.2.4. Active Transportation

This is a term most often used in North American literature

“Transportation” is a term generally used in the USA whereas in British English, the term used is “transport”. The term does appear in different contexts, but it is relatively rarely used in Europe.

3.2.5. Other remarks

Among other terms, the following were found in the literature:

- Active modes of travel
- Active modes of transportation
- Transport related physical activity
- Walking and bicycling for travel purposes
- Walking for transport
- Slower modes

Less defined terminology within the public health discipline

The terms used for what PASTA means with “active mobility” differs between disciplines. While “active transport” is most common in the transport discipline, “active travel” is most commonly used in the public health sector.

Further, within the public health sector, more articles don’t use a defined term, but rather explicitly explain what is studied (e.g. “walking and cycling for transport”). Within the transport discipline, almost all articles use a specific term. The use of “active mobility” is concentrated to the transport discipline.

3.3. What are the possible ambiguities?

Out of the literature review and expert input, the following possible ambiguities were identified:

- “Active mobility” may relate to forms of mobility not to do with transport e.g. mobility of

the elderly, social mobility.

- “Active transport” is commonly used within the biochemistry field. This is the term with the largest ambiguities.
- “Active transportation” is used within the logistics field.
- “Active travel” may be perceived as a form of “sporty holiday”.

Term favoured by PASTA

At the PASTA Consortium Meeting in Stockholm, April 24-25 2014, each consortium partner had two votes in deciding on which term to use in PASTA. “Active mobility” won the vote, followed by “active transport” and “active travel”. “Active transportation” didn’t receive any votes (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 PASTA consortium vote on which term to use in PASTA at the Stockholm meeting, April 24-25 2014.

3.4. Recommendations

The review of the literature and discussion with experts shows that there is no clear term to use in PASTA. Within certain countries and contexts, certain terms are favoured, and all terms are found to have ambiguities of some kind. There is no obvious choice, but based on the findings we would recommend to use the term “active mobility”.

This term is commonly used within the EU context, and favoured in the PASTA stakeholder meeting in Brussels in April 2014. The term was also favoured by the PASTA consortium at the Stockholm meeting in April 2014.

“Active mobility“ is the term that was recommended to be used in the PASTA project.

Given that there is no clear term to use in all contexts, we would also add the following:

- When publishing scientific articles on PASTA care should be taken to adapt the style to that of the journal as is normally practised. This means that the term “active mobility” may not be the best term to use.

- If it is a North American journal with North American spelling and terminology, the term “active transportation” may be most suitable.
- If it is a UK journal, the term to use would most likely be “active travel”.
- UK or Irish publications to the UK /Irish audience only (e.g. questionnaires used in London) would benefit from using the term “active travel”.
- Other publications to specific audiences should use the term most used for those audiences.

4. What is an active mobility measure?

4.1. Our definition

Active mobility measures are one of the core concepts in the PASTA project, since they will be evaluated during the project. To be clear on what we mean by “active mobility measures” (AM measures or AMM), but also to understand how the measures studied in the PASTA project fit in with other projects/initiatives, we have looked at the definition and classification of AMM.

The definition used in PASTA for an AMM is given in the box below:

An active mobility measure is an action undertaken in order to increase the level of active mobility (in a specified population). This ranges from changing urban infrastructure or introducing new policies to campaigns to change people’s transport behaviour.

4.2. Which terms are used (or not used)?

Understanding what AM measures are, and how other people refer to them requires looking at other ways to describe them. Apart from commonly being referred to as “measures”, they are also referred to as “interventions”. These terms are used almost synonymously, although “measures” are somewhat broader than “interventions”. In the health field, “intervention” is commonly used, and in transport “measure” is more often used.

However, it is often the case that no phrase at all is used to describe AM measures, rather the name of the measure itself is used without any mention of “intervention” or “measure” (e.g. active travel to school campaign).

“Measure” can be misinterpreted as a way to measure something (e.g. a measure of the level of cycling is km cycled).

4.3. Classification of measures

Within the PASTA project, it was important to develop a classification of measures to make sure we had a good understanding of what active mobility measures are, and to communicate internally and externally about AM measures. A preliminary classification of measures was included in the PASTA Description of Work (see Table). These measure classes are not fit for purpose as they are not all examples of measures (e.g. documentation, evaluation, research), they include descriptions of measures (“new”, “better”) and they mix what the measures do (e.g. infrastructure) and what the outcomes of the measures are (e.g. safety). It is necessary for the project to have a better measure classification.

Table 4 Original measure classification suggestion in PASTA description of work

Infrastructure	Safety improvements	Information (general campaigns)	Targeted campaigns, transport demand management	Better quality	New services	Policies, regulations, laws	Strategies, planning processes, administration	Documentation, evaluation, research
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Many different classifications of AM measures exist. These include classification by mode (walking, cycling, public transport, intermodal); by whether they are “hard” or “soft” measures; based on where they are implemented (workplace, school, community, etc); based on what they aim to achieve (accessibility, efficiency); or by how they are to be implemented (ITS, traffic management,); by who implements them (local authority, workplace, etc.); by the stages of change model (see e.g. Geelen, 2013); etc.

There are no standard, all-encompassing examples of measure classification across the board, as this depends – rightly so – on the purpose of the classification. In Northern America (and Canada) the “Four Es” classification is sometimes used including: engineering, education, encouragement, and enforcement, although it has also been suggested to include a fifth “E”: environment (Winters et al., 2011). The model is however, widely applied, not simply for classifying measures, but also as a method of working, and how to address different aspects of active mobility planning (see e.g. Walk Friendly Communities, 2010).

From the public health field, the Lancet published a Series on physical activity (Heath et al., 2012), including a classification of measures, consisting of three domains and five settings (taken from the guide to community preventative services). The Lancet states: “These domains are used because they conveniently capture most physical activity intervention strategies delivered throughout the world and consist of descriptors that are also in other international recommendation documents”.

The domains are:

- Campaigns and informational approaches
- Behavioural and social approaches
- Policy and environmental approaches

The settings are:

- School
- Workplace
- Community
- Clinical or primary health care
- Several settings

Of importance in the PASTA project is to find classifications that are relevant to the project, but will also be understandable to different communities. The classifications should cover as many AM measures as possible and also help in communicating what AM measures are.

The measure classification in the PASTA project should:

- Give an overview of what is being done to increase active mobility
- Fit within the PASTA framework
- Help in the communication of what active mobility measures are (be simple to understand)
- Cover a very wide range of AM measures

4.3.1. PASTA framework

The PASTA framework has been developed in parallel to the work of WP1, and is a conceptual model for the work that was done in PASTA (see Figure 6 and also Götschi et al., 2017). Here the ‘factors’ show different areas that affect AM, and provide a background to different areas to work on in increasing AM. At the same time, the outcomes are included in the PASTA framework as “observed behaviour” (or expected observed behaviour) covering physical activity behaviour, travel behaviour and safety events. For more details about the PASTA framework, the reader is referred to Götschi et al., 2017, including annexes therein.

Figure 6 The PASTA framework, which connects to the suggested measure categories. Notice that “Society and Culture” encompass all other attributes which include policy, natural environment, built environment, community, household and individual attributes. The trip (activity) is made within the context of this framework.

4.3.2. PASTA measure classification

Together, the four E’s classification as well as the measure categories (or ‘intervention domains’) from the Lancet series map well with the factors in the PASTA framework. To adapt them to PASTA categories we noted that the distinction between infrastructure measures, and non-infrastructure measures is much stronger in the field of transport than in health promotion, so we suggested to have a separate category for physical environment/infrastructure measures (“engineering” in the four Es, but going beyond this).

Policy measures are somewhat special since they lie behind other approaches. We suggested a separate category for strategic policy measures.

We suggested also that the ‘settings’ are instead divided by mode which the measure intends to affect (walking, cycling, public transport, other), as this was more important for PASTA.

Thus the measure classes are (see also Figure 7):

- **Strategic policy measures**

A policy represents a decision made by an individual or group which aims to achieve a specific aim or aims. A policy measure lies behind the other measures, since it constitutes a decision to do the other measures / package of measures. For example, a policy measure can be a cycling action plan: a decision to implement certain actions, and this action plan could include details of individual measures. Generally, policy measures are gathered in strategic policy packages, although this is not always the case.

- **Social environment measures**

Measures that manage demand for active mobility by changing travellers’ attitudes and behaviour⁴. These measures, include, for example, walking school bus, personalised travel planning, or broad information campaigns that aim to affect the way people think about their mobility. It also includes “process-related” measures which aim to change the way that working is done within administrations, as well as “health literacy” measures which aim to address how people obtain, read, understand and use healthcare information (in this case about active mobility).

A suggestion of subcategories here is:

- Pricing and incentives
- Information and communication

⁴For those in the transport community, these social environment measures are very similar to mobility management (MM) measures although MM focuses on managing the demand for car use. Mobility Management (MM) is a concept to promote sustainable transport and manage the demand for car use by changing travellers’ attitudes and behaviour (MAX, 2007).

- Promotion
- Education and training
- Physical environment/infrastructural measures

These are measures to change the physical environment such as infrastructure for walking and cycling, green area development, localisation, etc.
- Regulation and legislation measures

These are top-down measures which can range over different geographical levels: national level, city level, work place etc. For example, legislation which allows right turn at traffic lights for cyclists, or low emission zones.

Note that single measures can belong to more than one category; i.e. these categories are not mutually exclusive. Measures may further also be single measures or part of a package or programme of measures.

The ‘settings’ from the Lancet categorisation still apply, but of more importance in the PASTA context is the mode it intends to affect. Thus the application gives four categories:

- Walking
- Cycling
- Public transport
- Other (e.g. car-sharing, skateboarding, etc.)

Figure 7 Different types of AM measures by setting/mode and different classes of measure. Strategic policy is a measure class, but lies behind all other measure classes as well.

Direct and indirect active mobility measures

It is important to note that while some measures directly aim at increasing levels of active mobility, other measures can not directly be considered as AM measures, but nevertheless as indirect AM measures. The focus of the PASTA project was direct AM measures.

Direct AM measures aim to increase active mobility.

Indirect AM measures have other aims but increase active mobility through creating better conditions for walking, cycling and public transport (through increased relative attractiveness of these options).

4.4. Examples of measures

To give examples of different types of active mobility measures that have been implemented, a review was performed. This, in a first step, included a review of scientific articles to understand the use and terminology of “active mobility” and “active mobility measures”. In this broad search, 31 articles on measures were recorded with examples of AM measures. They included the following types of measures: workplace intervention; school trip intervention; walking school buses; walking and cycling infrastructure; promotional campaign; congestion charging scheme; walking plan; large-scale multi-modal programs.

To complement this search, further searches were made in other databases to identify examples of active mobility measures. This consisted of a search primarily of the Eltis⁵ database of case studies (which has input from a wide range of projects on transport and mobility), the CIVITAS⁶ database of measures, and Max EVA⁷ which includes information about evaluation of mobility management measures. These databases concentrate on measures in transport and mobility, with no explicit focus on health.

The examples gathered cover the categories as defined above, and range from small scale implementation to large scale comprehensive planning approaches. This review helped in identifying the types of measures that would later be studied in the PASTA project and which were included in the PASTA good practice guide. The collection of examples was used as input to the collection of good practices⁸, and helped to define the fields of interest to collect for the good practice guide. This includes: type of action, transport mode, innovation aspect, whether it addresses both health and planning, whether there is existence of institutional cooperation, whether there are perceived positive benefits (in increasing AM), whether there are evaluated positive benefits (in increasing AM) and whether there is transferability potential.

Of the examples that were collected it is worth to note that there were few examples of public transport and examples which had a direct ambition in multi-modality (i.e. combination of public transport with walking or cycling). There were also far fewer examples of regulation and legislation than social or physical environment measures. This is due mainly to the fact that regulation and legislation are primarily related to prohibiting car traffic rather than having a direct aim to increase AM modes.

Examples of physical environment measures include:

- Cycle Super Highways
- Public bike rental
- Bicycle and pedestrian bridge

⁵ www.eltis.org

⁶ www.civitas.eu

⁷ www.epomm.eu/maxeva

⁸ Collection of Good Practices from PASTA project published September 2017

- Floating walkway
- Park and bike terminal
- Pedestrian safety crossing

Examples of social environment measures include:

- Stakeholder consultation for cycling
- No ridiculous car trips
- Pedelec testing for senior citizens
- School cycling campaign / Cycling exam for children / Walking / Cycling bus / Safer routes to school
- Workplace cycle challenge / Company bikes instead of cars / Workplace travel plans national programme

And those measures which include an element of regulation / legislation include:

- Public transport priority
- Strolling zones
- 30 km/h zones

A full list of measures collected is included in Annex – Examples of AMM. Most of the measures do not include a health component. Although they aim to increase levels of active mobility, the aim was not related explicitly to increase levels of physical activity. The notable examples are measures that involve collaboration with health services to encourage patients to use active mobility in travelling to and from a health centre / hospital.

Strategic policy measures lie behind these measures in almost all cases, since most of the examples were implemented by a public authority which requires political approval and motivation and implementation within a policy framework.

Pioneering cities

In looking at the examples of AMM, it was clear that the scope of measures differs considerable between cases. Pioneering cities/regions address health issues in land use and transport planning with innovative thinking. Traditional actions to make streets greener, safer and more inviting to pedestrians, cyclists and public transport users are combined with suitable and supportive policy frameworks to increase the level of physical activity and replace car trips with active travel. In identifying pioneering cities, we look to cities which have a high mode share of actively mobile modes, and a comprehensive approach and policy in increasing levels of active mobility. A first identification of these pioneering cities is done by identifying cities with a high level of walking, cycling and public transport in the trip modal split. This can be done using the EPOMM TEMS – modal split tool⁹. Setting minimum levels of 15 % trips for walking, cycling and public transport and car trips to less than 40 %

⁹ <http://www.epomm.eu/tems>

brings up 9 cities with population over 100 000 (of the 299 in the database): Amsterdam, Copenhagen, Hannover, Karlsruhe, Freiburg, Odense, Basel, Potsdam, and Heidelberg. All of these cities have comprehensive planning documents which concentrate on increasing levels of active mobility and reducing car use. Further analysis of pioneering cities was done in identifying good practices in a later part of the PASTA project.

Evaluation

One of the elements that was checked in screening examples of AMM was whether an evaluation of the measure existed. The evaluation methodologies differed considerably between cases: ranging from comprehensive before and after travel surveys to subjective assessments of the project team on the success of the measure. Details of the level of evaluation have been included when looking at the examples in existing databases (see Annex).

4.5. Recommendations

“Active mobility measure” is a wide term applicable to most actions taken to increase active mobility. The PASTA consortium voted unanimously for using “Active mobility measure” as the standard term to describe actions taken to increase the level of “active mobility”, whereas “active mobility intervention” is a narrower term focused on activities undertaken at a certain point in time.

For the PASTA project, we suggested the following classification of measures:

- By mode: walking, cycling, public transport, other
- By domain: strategic policy, social environment, physical environment/infrastructure, regulation and legislation

These categories:

- Give an overview of what is being done to increase active mobility
- Fit within the PASTA framework
- Help in the communication of what active mobility measures are
- Cover a very wide range of AM measures

5. Glossary

To get to a common understanding of terminology in the project, a glossary was set up on the shared PASTA drive. This document was free for any members of the consortium to update or comment. The document consisted of 6 fields: term; description; examples; references; changes; and comments.

An overview of the glossary, but only including the first two fields, can be found in Annex-PASTA Glossary.

Certain terms were of particular importance to define for the PASTA project, and these include the definitions of “good practice AM measure”, “innovative AM measure” and “successful AM measure”. These terms were presented at the PASTA consortium meeting in April 2014 to ensure feedback was received. The definitions in PASTA are:

Good practice AM measure: A good practice AM measure is a successful measure. A good practice considered for PASTA is characterised by the following attributes:

- Includes an innovative approach beyond the common practice. (An innovative measure is one which exploits existing conditions to maximum effect in a new way).
- The measure has led to an increase of AM; has been evaluated and/or measured; or has been perceived as successful.

Innovative AM measure: An innovative measure is one which exploits existing conditions to maximum effect in a new way.

Successful AM measure: A measure with proven results on active mobility outcomes. Success (ie whether a measure 'worked' or 'did not work') of a measure may not easily be transferable because it is unique in term of its content (the detail of the measure/project) and its context (the social, community, and topographical environment). Success should also specify why a measure is (or is not) effective, in what ways, for whom, and in what circumstances.

6. Factors

6.1. What are these factors, and why do we care?

A central tenet of the PASTA project is that increasing levels of active mobility is a positive thing that will bring benefit to European society. The extent of these benefits, and in-depth understanding of the links between active mobility measures, levels of active mobility, and physical activity was studied in the PASTA project. At the basis of this is an understanding of what we know about what affects levels of active mobility. Factors that affect active mobility include determinants and correlates of active mobility (see chapter 5 for definitions). They give us information on what factors can affect the success of active mobility measures, and which factors affect the implementation of AMM.

A review of which factors are known to affect AM helped us to define what data needed to be collected in case study cities of the project as background information for the context of the study. If it is known, for example, that hilliness or climate in a city can affect levels of active mobility, then data on this should be collected as background to the longitudinal study done in PASTA. The review also gives some input on factors that could or should be considered in the design and implementation of AMM.

The collection of factors affecting AM is structured along the lines of the PASTA framework as described in section 6.2. This framework provides a classification of factors and areas in which the search for factors is made. The search is made broadly, and a summary is given over the direction (if known) of the relationship between the factor and active mobility (e.g. extreme weather reduces levels of active mobility) as well as the reference to the source material.

6.2. Factors within the PASTA framework

The PASTA framework provides a way to classify the different factors. The proposed framework presents AM as a more or less hierarchically structured system of behavioural choices and factors affecting these. Hierarchical levels consist of context, such as society/culture, spatial and social environment; the individual; trips; mode and route chosen.

At most of these levels, individuals consider several options and make decisions, based on a range of criteria. A main goal of AM behaviour research is to properly understand which factors affect these decisions, which ultimately would allow shaping policies in ways to efficiently promote AM.

The framework is based on the experience gained in the PASTA project and the review of selected publications (e.g. Pikora et al., 2003; Schepers et al., 2014; Ogilvie et al., 2012), It also relates to the socio-ecological model which shows that levels of physical activity and active mobility depend on several different strands; the individual, social environment, physical environment and policy (Sallis et al., 2006).

6.3. Overview of the different factors

The following sections contain an overview of the findings.

6.3.1. Policies

A policy represents a decision made by an individual or group which aims to achieve a specific aim or aims (see chapter 4). In PASTA, a specific aim is to increase levels of active mobility or to decrease levels of car use (making active mobility relatively more attractive). Policies can include community-scale urban design, land use policies; regulations; planning, pricing (parking, road, fuel), restrictions on car use, national and regional travel plans. This section takes a look at findings on what is known from the scientific literature about the impact of policies and measures on levels of active mobility.

Measures, studies and study methodologies are heterogeneous and vary considerably in type and quality, with few meeting rigorous standards (Pucher et al., 2010; Scheepers et al., 2014). Valid and reliable data collection methods and appropriate statistical analysis are necessary to assess whether a measure has an effect on active travel. Study methodologies in the literature varied widely, including both stated and revealed preference, individual- and aggregate-level analysis, experimental and non-experimental designs (Pucher et al., 2010; Scheepers et al., 2014).

The vast majority of measures do not include an evaluation component that would provide evidence of the impact of the measure on the amount of cycling or walking (Pucher et al., 2010). If studies do evaluate a measure, most studies do not report how the effect of measures on active mobility vary between demographic or socioeconomic groups (Ogilvie et al., 2007; Scheepers et al., 2014), and do not include results on statistical significance of effects (Scheepers et al., 2014).

Some policies or measures that promote active mobility do not necessarily target walking and cycling per se, but instead have an indirect effect by discouraging car travel and thereby promoting alternatives (de Nazelle et al., 2011). For example, a new railway station can promote walking and cycling (Ogilvie et al., 2004) or a car-sharing scheme can induce a shift to active modes (Lane, 2005). Some studies focus on cycling and walking measures separately, and do not consider active mobility as a whole; this may result in pedestrians changing to cycling and not having the same gain from a health point of view. Measures to increase public transport are not included in the studies found, only those that look at shift from car to walking or cycling (or both). Public transport measures can also suffer from the same problem in inciting a mode shift from walking and cycling, and thus leading to less overall physical activity from active mobility, for example the introduction of free public transport passes can boost public transport ridership but induce less cycling (Heinen et al., 2013).

Walking and cycling tend to increase with the cost of driving (Handy et al., 2014). Of course, walking and cycling are almost cost free, with the exception of the initial purchase of the bicycle and some ongoing maintenance costs. But evidence suggests that the cost of alternative modes, e.g. parking fees, fuel taxes, road user charges as well as financial incentives such as free parking or subsidised public transport tickets, affect active mobility (and public transport use) by making the alternatives more or less attractive (Handy et al., 2010a; Buehler et al., 2012; Handy & Xing 2010).

Bundles of strategies are often implemented together, ranging from promotional campaigns to changes in the physical infrastructure (e.g. sidewalk improvement and bike lanes), making it difficult to isolate specific elements that may change travel behaviours but also suggesting that multi-pronged strategies are most effective at creating change (de Nazelle et al., 2011; Pucher et al., 2010; Yang et al., 2010; Scheepers et al., 2014). The cases reviewed in Pucher et al. (2010), Krizek et al. (2009) and Scheepers et al. (2014) suggest that a comprehensive approach produces a much greater impact on bicycling than individual measures that are not coordinated.

In general, the most robust evidence of effectiveness was concentrated around measures targeted at motivated groups of volunteers (Ogilvie et al., 2004; Ogilvie et al., 2007). Neither these measures nor their observed effects are necessarily applicable to larger, less selected populations.

Summary, and areas for future research

In summary, there is very little known about the effectiveness of measures in increasing levels of active mobility, although the little that is known seems to indicate that comprehensive approaches would seem to be more effective than individual measures.

The best available evidence is somewhat skewed in favour of studies of measures that seem easier to evaluate, or perhaps easier to randomise, typically individually focused interventions such as brief advice or pedometers, often studied in small samples with motivated respondents (Ogilvie et al., 2007; Scheepers et al., 2014). There is also a publication bias towards studies finding positive effects of an intervention (Kassavou et al., 2013; Scheepers et al., 2014).

Additionally, the evaluation of measures in cross-sectional study design poses questions regarding causal inference. There are insufficient longitudinal data to ascertain what specific policy or change in the built environment would result in a change in travel habits (de Nazelle et al., 2011; Heath et al., 2006). Preference should be given to controlled before-and-after experimental studies, but they are more rare (Yang et al., 2010). Policies and measures may have very different outcomes on the long or short-terms, and these are not captured without adequate study design (Kassavou et al., 2013; Krizek et al., 2009; Macmillan et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2010).

Studies rarely include details on the effects beyond levels of active mobility to wider physical activity effects (total physical activity), or on general levels of physical activity of individuals who are affected by the measures (is it novice cyclists or existing cyclists) (Ogilvie et al., 2007; Yang et al., 2010). This has an impact on the health impacts of measures.

6.3.2. Physical environment

Factors in the physical environment include transport options, the built environment and natural environment. 'Transport options' refers to the availability of different options to reach numerous destinations, and is essentially a question of accessibility to destinations by different transport modes. This is also partly covered by the built environment which includes infrastructure for different transport modes. The natural environment includes factors such as weather and topology. This section does not separate these subcategories, and an overview is given below of how all factors under 'physical environment' affect levels of active

mobility.

The way that an urban environment is designed can influence the propensity of inhabitants to participate in active mobility (Sallis et al., 2012; Aldred & Woodcock, 2008). Recent reviews on the determinants of bicycle commuting highlighted a need for a more comprehensive approach and focus on bicycle-specific factors, particularly of the built environment (Heinen et al., 2010a; Owen et al., 2004; Saelens et al., 2003). Additional research into neighbourhood design features that support bicycling and walking (i.e. have a high bikeability and/or walkability index) has been warranted, as such features have been shown to not only increase bicycling (Pucher et al., 2010) and walking (Eriksson et al., 2013) but also neighbourhood-wide physical activity (Brown et al., 2013). High density and mixed land use lead to a higher cycle share (Heinen et al., 2010). Geographic information systems (GIS) have been used to investigate whether objective measures (physical features) of an urban commute environment, such as local topography, affect active mobility participation (Troped et al., 2001; Rodríguez & Joo 2004; McGinn et al., 2007; Evenson et al., 2009).

Positive associations have been shown between cycling behaviour and the physical and functional components of a commute environment, such as infrastructure, street connectivity and facility provision (Panter & Jones, 2010; Molina-García et al., 2010; Titze et al., 2008; Owen et al., 2004; Prins et al., 2016). For example, previous research with young adults in Spain investigated attitudes and behaviour of active commuting to the place of study to show positive-correlations with walking and cycling facilities as well as opinion of physical self-efficacy, however also negative-correlations with planning and psychosocial barriers as well as access to private motor vehicles (Molina-García et al., 2010). According to a review by Heinen et al. (2010), cyclists prefer it when there is bicycle infrastructure that is continuous and on roads with no parking, and the preference is for dedicated infrastructure with as few stops as possible. However, they do not draw conclusions on whether the presence and continuity of bicycle infrastructure leads to more cycling or not. Results from the iConnect study (Ogilvie et al., 2011; Ogilvie et al., 2012) show that new walking and cycling infrastructure, while it does not have a noticeable effect on mode shift from car to walking and cycling (Brand et al., 2014) did have an effect on overall levels of physical activity (particularly among non-car users) (Goodman et al., 2014; Sahlqvist et al., 2013), although the infrastructure primarily attracted existing walkers and cyclists of higher socio-economic classes (Goodman et al., 2013).

While it has been shown that the proximity of public transport to commute addresses is not significantly-associated with active mobility use (Molina-García et al., 2010), physical characteristics of commute routes, rather than the origins or destinations, have been shown as more influential (Winters et al., 2010). Further, bicyclists have been shown to travel longer distances to use bicycle infrastructure such as bicycle lanes (Dill & Gliebe, 2008). This suggests that topographical and built-environmental features (such as slope and traffic calming measures, respectively) are strong determinants for bicycle commuting participation. Regarding slope, this is strengthened by findings in Heinen et al. (2010) which concludes that slopes have a negative impact on cycling. The seasons also play a role on level of cycling, as does the chance of rain, low temperatures and darkness (Heinen et al., 2010).

The existence and interaction of psychological or physical motivators and barriers require further investigation to inform policy for increasing active mobility participation (Panter &

Jones, 2010). For example, while it might seem most logical to invest in infrastructure such as bicycle lanes and parking, it has been recently shown that physical barriers may not be the most discouraging to bicycle commute participation (Nkurunziza et al., 2012). Further, it has been stated that influencing personal perception may be enough to change behaviour rather than improving the physical environment itself (Dewulf et al., 2012).

It is important to note however that elements of the physical environment are perceived by people in different ways – referred to as the ‘subjective’ perception of the environment. Bicycle commuters may perceive more possibilities and are therefore more motivated for bicycle commuting participation compared to non-active commuters (Bamberg et al., 2003). Further, bicycle commuters, however, may be more likely to report positive or negative environmental elements, such as aesthetics and air pollution (Panter & Jones, 2010). While it has been previously shown that air pollution exposure during work-related commuting is highly-recognised by commuters (independent of travel mode), it was not seen as a major barrier to active mobility participation (Badland & Duncan, 2009). On the other hand, perception of the commute environment has been studied to find that aesthetic, green and perceptibly-safe urban environments are the most stimulating to walking (Pikora et al., 2003) and bicycle commuting (Wahlgren & Schantz, 2012). Conversely, it has been shown that non-bicycle commuters perceive more barriers and are therefore less motivated to participate in bicycle commuting than individuals of equivalent status that are already commuting by bicycle (Gatersleben & Appleton, 2007; Geus, 2008). The perception of ability to perform bicycle commuting, and therefore the degree of participation, may also be influenced by cultural attitudes and road-use education.

Previous research has identified that the practical factors of reduced cost and time, and increased independence associated with bicycle use are recognised as important when choosing a commute transport mode (Simons et al., 2013). In fact, common determinants of bicycle commuting in different countries, cultures and geographies have been investigated to highlight that cost, travel time, effort demand and safety were all important for bicycle commuters (Heinen et al., 2010). A recent telephone interview of more than 1,000 randomly-selected Copenhagen residents reported quickness, convenience and cheapness (in decreasing order of frequency) as reasons for cycling to and from work or study (City of Copenhagen, 2013). An Australian study of young adults attending university found that while travel time was the most significant barrier to active mobility, the potential of saving money by performing active mobility was a motivator to participation (Shannon et al., 2006). Therefore, if public transport is economically-attractive and integrated with active mobility modes (such as allowing bicycles on-board buses) then bicycle commuting may be more viable for individuals commuting longer distances.

Both psychological and environmental factors appear to be significant correlates of active mobility. The way in which they interact, however, is not well understood. Heterogeneity in study designs and measurement methods limit the ability to generalise many findings. To develop effective measures, promotion to integrate walking and cycling into everyday activities is suggested (Panter & Jones, 2010).

Summary, and areas for future research

In summary, there are a number of physical environment factors that affect the levels of active mobility including the existence and quality of walking and cycling infrastructure,

weather, and topographical features. However, it is important to note that the perception of the physical environment differs between individuals. Thus one person may view the same physical environment as good enough to cycle, while another will view it as inadequate.

It has been highlighted that further investigation is needed into the existence and interaction of psychological or physical motivators and barriers to more effectively inform policy for increasing active mobility participation (e.g. Panter & Jones, 2010).

Another area for further research is in the need for a more comprehensive approach and focus on bicycle-specific factors, particularly of the built environment (such as bicycle-specific infrastructure, presence of traffic lights and stop signs, and pavement quality) (Heinen et al., 2010; Owen et al., 2004; Saelens et al., 2003). Such features (as components of the bikeability and/or walkability index) have been shown to not only increase bicycling (Pucher et al., 2010) but also neighbourhood-wide physical activity (Brown et al., 2013). Geographic information systems (GIS) provide the opportunity for both a broad and focused assessment of an urban commute environment for these factors (Troped et al., 2001; Rodríguez & Joo, 2004; McGinn et al., 2007; Evenson et al., 2009). Further, we need transferability of this knowledge with research conducted across a wider range of cities/countries (Heinen et al., 2010).

Furthermore, there needs to be a stronger focus on determinants research with improved causal inference rather than repetition of cross-sectional correlates studies (Bauman et al., 2012). That is, we need “data on mode choice (...) gathered over a long period of time; longitudinal research would allow one to investigate this causal relationship, and such research is clearly needed, on the grounds that people find it difficult to state their daily choices over long time periods; moreover, longitudinal research would allow one to detect the most important factors at the level of the individual. Longitudinal research is therefore needed in order to examine determinants for daily choices and therefore cycling frequency” (Heinen et al., 2010).

6.3.3. Safety related factors

Safety related factors are important in the determination of which mode of transport a person chooses. Safety relates both to ‘objective’ safety (i.e. a measurable number of incidents, injuries, fatalities, etc) and ‘subjective’ safety which is the perceived safety of individuals (i.e. an individual may choose to drive a car and not to walk because they perceive it to be unsafe to walk even if there have not been any safety incidents for pedestrians along the route they will take). This section looks at which factors affect safety levels which in turn affect levels of active mobility.

To investigate determinants of crash risks a wide range of study designs are applied. A number of reports and reviews provide helpful overviews (Wegman et al. (2012), Schepers et al. (2014), Ragland et al. (2013), and Zegeer (2010). Selected determinants are described below.

Traffic conditions, in particular volume and speed, are certainly important for cycling safety, but empirical evidence is rare (Elvik, 2009; Strauss, Miranda-Moreno et al., 2013; Strauss, Miranda-Moreno et al., 2014). Speed of vehicles involved in a collision is clearly related to

injury severity (American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials, 2010), but severe injuries may be less frequent on roads with higher traffic volumes (Klop and Khattak, 1999). Nordback et al. (2014) found that in Boulder, CO (USA), higher traffic volumes of both motorised vehicles and bicycles reduce cyclist crash rates (i.e. less than linear increase in crashes) at intersections. Bunn et al. (2003) found that traffic calming schemes reduce fatal crashes by a third and crashes with injuries by about 10%. The majority of crash victims in this meta-analysis were pedestrians, although the safety improvements for cyclists may be similar (Wegman, Zhang et al., 2012). Volume and speed of motorised traffic should be regarded as key criteria for the choice of bicycle infrastructure measures. Higher volumes and speeds call for higher degrees of physical separation of cyclists and motorised traffic, and vice versa, mixed traffic is more adequate with lower volumes and slower speeds (Land Transport Safety Authority, 2004; Wegman, Zhang et al., 2012). The same logic applies to mixed traffic of cyclists and pedestrians, but few studies have looked at conflicts between cyclists and pedestrians (Haworth and Schramm, 2011; Shaw, Poulos et al., 2014).

Teschke et al. provide a rare study on crash risks of cycling in relation to different types of infrastructure (2012). In their study of bicycle crashes in Vancouver and Toronto, Canada, the probability for a crash was almost ten times lower on a cycle track, compared to a major street with parked cars. Lusk et al. (2011) observed approximately 30% lower crash risks on cycle tracks, compared to comparable roads without cycle tracks. In an earlier GIS based analysis of Toronto cyclists, Aultman-Hall and Kaltenecker (1999) observed higher collision rates on roads, compared with off-road paths and sidewalks. However, for falls and injuries, the rates were lowest on roads. Overall, rates for all incidents were 26 to 68 times higher than for driving.

In a review of earlier studies on infrastructure and cycling safety, Reynolds et al. (2009) concluded that there was “a principal trend that clearly-marked, bike-specific facilities (i.e. cycle tracks at roundabouts, bike routes, bike lanes, and bike paths) were consistently shown to provide improved safety for cyclists compared to on-road cycling with traffic or off-road with pedestrians and other users.”

Distraction of drivers and pedestrians by cell phone use has emerged as an important risk factor. Legislating bodies all around the world have issued regulations on cell phone use while driving, and new research also looks at the effects of distracted walking and cycling (Kircher et al., 2014). Large vehicles, such as trucks, pose particular risks to cyclists due to their extended blind spots, which can cause dangerous conflicts in turning movements (Morgan, Dale et al., 2010).

A controversially debated topic are bicycle helmets (Robinson, 2007). It is undisputed that helmets reduce the risk of severe head injuries in a bike crash by about 50 percent (Elvik, 2011). Cycling advocates, however, point out that helmet wearing rates are lowest in countries where cycling is safest, e.g. the Netherlands. Some countries have or debate mandatory helmet wearing laws, which are criticised for putting an (additional) burden on cyclists (Robinson, 2003). Overall, evidence on preventive effects of helmet laws is insufficient to weigh injury prevention effects against unintended public health consequences from less people cycling (Grant and Rutner, 2004; Robinson, 2006; De Jong 2012; Fyhri, Bjørnskau et al., 2012).

Also, often changes in cycling are not attributable to specific projects (e.g. infrastructure types) but rather the result of broader schemes or policies. Safety impact models therefore sometimes apply non-linear crash risk functions, which reflect that with increasing levels of cycling (through whatever measures) crash rates increase less than proportionately (Scheepers and Heinen, 2013; Woodcock, Givoni et al., 2013), a phenomenon referred to as “safety in numbers” (Jacobsen, 2003; Elvik, 2009). While this relationship has been observed widely (Jacobsen, 2003; Robinson, 2005; Elvik, 2009; Gotschi, 2011), its interpretation has been criticised for being too focused on one of the two possible causal directions – the higher number of cyclists improving safety – while equally, more safety increasing the numbers of cyclists (“numbers in safety”) would, and likely has, lead to the same non-linear relationship (Bhatia and Wier, 2011). Pathways in both directions are certainly plausible but there is no research available that could quantify the pathway specific contributions to safety or numbers, respectively. It should be noted that the direction of causality does not affect impact calculations. Caution should however be exercised when drawing policy conclusions based on the correlation of levels and safety of cycling.

Another related topic is perceived safety (“subjective” safety), which may or may not be correlated with objective safety (Elvik and Bjørnskau, 2005). More importantly, it is a crucial determinant of cycling behaviour (Noland, 1995; Ogilvie, Egan et al., 2004; Carver, Salmon et al., 2005; Hoehner, Brennan Ramirez et al., 2005; Kerr, Rosenberg et al., 2006; Jacobsen, Racioppi et al., 2009; Reynolds, Harris et al., 2009; Nelson and Woods, 2010; Winters and Teschke, 2010; Heinen, Maat et al., 2011; Van Dyck, Cerin et al., 2012; Morckel and Terzano, 2014; Sanders, 2015). As such, addressing the issue of perceived safety is primarily an effort to promote cycling. In most cases, increasing objective safety is certainly a necessary part to improving perceived safety, but it may not necessarily be sufficient. Other factors, such as providing (potential) cyclists with facilities and opportunities to gain positive experiences, including formal and informal learning and training options, facilities protected from motorised traffic, such as trails and traffic calmed zones, as well as a general sense of public acceptance, support or even enthusiasm for cycling may be equally important in influencing perceived safety of cycling (Pucher and Buehler, 2008).

Summary, and areas for future research

Cycling levels are related to safety and perceived safety levels (also known as ‘objective’ and ‘subjective’ safety respectively). There are a number of factors that affect objective safety for active modes including infrastructure, traffic conditions, driver behaviour. Perceived safety is affected by numerous factors from social factors (e.g. public acceptance/opinion) to infrastructure (level of well-lit, accessible, segregated infrastructure). The relationships are often non-linear and there are complexities arising between objective and subjective safety and levels of active mobility.

There needs to be a stronger focus on determinants research with improved causal inference using longitudinal study designs. Longitudinal research is needed in order to examine determinants for perceived safety and how it affects levels of active mobility. Also, studies on different groups such as children is needed to enhance knowledge on how to increase safety and perceived safety in the whole population.

6.3.4. Social environment

This section looks at social environmental factors such as social norm and social support, and how they affects AM behaviour.

Webb & Sheeran (2006) state that, “the most effective way to change behaviour is through social support and pressure”. Social support and social pressure are two distinct types of influences on behaviour. Concerning social pressure, or social norms, Webb & Sheeran (2006) are not alone in the statement as Bonsall, Conner & Darnton (2009) also suggest that an individual’s longing to be approved by others can be used to be a key motivator of behaviour change (Allcott, 2011).

There are two types of social norm that influence an individual’s intention to behave in a certain way, the first type of social norm is a subjective norm whereby the behaviour receives approval or disapproval by others (Thøgersen, 2006; Ajzen, 1991). The subjective norm is an individual’s belief that is based on what other people think about a given behaviour and not on a personal belief (Jackson, 2005). Subjective norms have been found to be influential on pro-environmental behaviour and is demonstrated in work that Thøgersen (2006) highlights by Bamberg & Schmidt (2003) (car use) and Bratt (1999) (recycling behaviour).

The second type of social norm is a descriptive norm; this is when an individual has a perception of what normal behaviour is for individuals like themselves (Biel & Thøgersen, 2007; Thøgersen, 2006). In the case of walking and cycling individuals that see other people like them carrying out these behaviours are more likely to walk or cycle themselves (Ogilvie et al., 2011). Cialdini, Kallgren & Reno (1991) state that descriptive norms are relevant as they provide source of information on how an individual should behave under certain conditions. Social norms also have an influence internally, within an individual, where they can inform personal norms (Klöckner, 2004; Klöckner & Matthies, 2004; Schwartz, 1977).

Goodman, Green and Woodcock (2014) carried out research on the Bicycle Sharing System (BSS) in London and identified that a barrier to individuals cycling was the perception of who would normally cycle. The specialist clothing that individuals saw cyclists wearing resulted in perceptions of cycling being a sporty activity and not something that people like the individual would do (Goodman, Green and Woodcock, 2014). Goodman, Green & Woodcock (2014) found that the BSS encouraged individuals to cycle in a recreational manner to travel around London. This change occurred due to a development of a new social norm where individuals saw others in casual clothes, like themselves, cycling which encouraged them to try cycling themselves (Goodman, Green & Woodcock, 2014; Fishman, Washington & Haworth, 2012; Green, Steinbach & Datta, 2012).

Goodman, Green & Woodcock’s (2014) research shows that social norms can be targeted in order to move people from the precontemplation stage of the Transtheoretical Model to the contemplation stage where, as they have seen individuals like themselves cycling, they themselves believe that they can cycle – the social norm here has also increased perceived behavioural control. This demonstrates the influence of social norms on perceived behavioural control and highlights how an intervention that targets social norms, such as a BSS, can also influence other psychological determinants of behaviour. This claim is supported by academics such as Bamberg et al. (2011), who suggests that the key to

encouraging individuals to change their behaviour is by making social norms more salient during the early stages of behaviour change interventions. This targets both contemplators and precontemplators by normalising the target behaviour and so encourages individuals in these stages of change to progress towards the preparation stage.

Previous work by Bamberg, Hunecke & Blöbaum (2007) on travel behaviour in two German cities shows that social norms serve to moderate the relationship between personal norms and behaviour. Social norms in one of the German cities studied by Bamberg, Hunecke & Blöbaum (2007) were concluded to have a large impact on people's intention to use public transport. This shows the importance of understanding and utilising social norms in behaviour change interventions as social norms have an influence on active travel behaviour and also on public transport use. Both of these forms of transport reduce the negative impact on the environment and in the case of active transport there are also health benefits compared with using a personal vehicle (Oja, Vuori & Paronen, 1998).

Social support refers to perception of being cared for and belonging to a certain group of people. The role and composition of the social network from which an individual receives support differs depending on cultures/geographies (Na et al, 2015). How the social network perceives cycling can make a difference as to how likely a person is to cycle; for example in Madrid a study by Muñoz et al (2013) shows that the opinions of the family play a strong role in whether someone decides to cycle or not. This result is also found in a study from Flanders in Belgium (Geus et al, 2008) which shows the importance of social support for cycling and walking among work-aged men in the country, particularly close family, but also friends. This builds on work showing that participation in physical activity is impacted by social support (De Bourdeaudhuij et al., 2003), as well as participation in recreational walking (Duncan and Mummery, 2005).

Following on from this, the “normalisation” of cycling as a mode is also important for whether people decide to cycle or not. A study of cycling in six USA cities shows that the perception of who else is cycling plays a role in whether someone chooses to cycle (Xing et al 2010). Similarly, the normalisation of a public transport link plays a role as to whether it is used or not (Ogilvie et al, 2016), and the normalisation of cycling can be brought about by seeing others “like myself” cycling (Goodman et al, 2014).

Summary, and areas for future research

The social environment plays an important role in determining whether individuals will partake in active mobility. Whether an individual partakes in active mobility or not depends on how they perceive active mobility, and this depends on the prevailing social norms, their social support network and whether active mobility is “normal”. Social norms can be subjective (what others think about how an individual should behave) or descriptive (what the individual thinks is normal). Both affect how an individual can perceive active mobility, and whether they engage in it. Promoters of active mobility can work on altering the social environment in order to increase levels of active mobility. For example, certain measures, such as the introduction of a bike share system can change the perception of what cycling is (make it more normal), thus making it socially acceptable to cycle and more likely that an individual will engage in active mobility. More work needs to be done on how these social environment factors differ in different contexts, and how they should best be applied in the prevailing cultural/geographic context.

6.3.5. Socio-demographic factors, household etc.

This section reviews the socio-demographic and socio-economic factors/ associates/ determinants. These include factors relating to socio-economic status, household composition, car ownership, etc.

There is ample evidence that active mobility is associated with gender, age, physical ability, level of education, household income, household structure (and presence of children), vehicle access (both car and non-motorised modes), driver's licence status, ethnicity, employment and working situation, an active lifestyle, and other socio-demographic factors (see references throughout this section). Handy et al. (2014) reviewed studies identifying key factors associated with transport cycling and found that socio-demographic characteristics have a strong connection to cycling, particularly gender, income and age, with apparent differences in associations between socio-economic factors and utility and recreation-only cycling (Goodman, 2011; Heesch et al., 2014; Pucher et al., 2011).

Young people tend to have high rates of walking and cycling. Some older people have high rates of walking for transport and exercise but there can be substantial intra-urban variability in walking behaviours of seniors with different socio-economic and demographic profiles (Moniruzzaman et al., 2013). The factors that influence children's travel behaviour have changed in recent years, with the development of car-oriented lifestyles, increased numbers of mothers in employment and changes in attitudes towards children's independent mobility (Mackett, 2013; McDonald, 2012). For younger children, insufficient household income, having an older sibling, and living in a neighbourhood that is not excellent for raising children, or characterised with high decay, can be predictive of greater likelihood of using active mobility (Pabayo et al., 2012; Panter et al., 2013). At the other end of the economic spectrum, increasing household income and increasing car ownership are consistently associated with lower rates of AM among children (Pont et al., 2009). In contrast, a longitudinal study in São Paulo found rates of bicycle use rising over time among the richest quartile but total cycling rates dropped from 1997 to 2012 due to decreasing rates among the poor (Hérick Sá et al., 2016).

People who do not have a car or driver's licence tend to rely on public transport, walking and cycling for travel from place to place. In the UK, for example, active mobility participation is generally greater in younger people and those without access to a car or van (Panter et al., 2013; Adams, 2005). Physical ability is obviously important: studies have shown that cycling ability is an important predictor of who cycles and how frequently (Handy et al., 2010). One study found that bicycle use is associated with public transport use, vehicles per person, being physically active, and being in good health (Moudon et al., 2005). Some people with impairments rely on walking and cycling, and may require facilities with suitable design features, such as ramps for walkers and wheelchairs. There is evidence of inequality in bicycle ownership and use among children from different ethnic groups (Christie et al., 2011), although the direction of inequality is largely context specific (Pont et al., 2009). Many lower-income people tend to rely on active modes for transport (McDonald, 2008). Bicycle commuting is popular among higher income professionals (Dill & Gliebe, 2008). Being sufficiently active through active mobility was additionally associated with being unemployed, being in a less affluent social class, and leaving full time education at an older age.

Heinen et al. (2011) offer a more cautious assessment of the importance of socio-economic

factors: “There is a relationship between socio-economic factors and cycling to/from work, but we lack clarity on both the direction of this relationship, and its causality.” Recent studies have begun to unravel the role of attitudes and preferences that affect cycling (Heinen et al., 2011; Dill & Voros, 2007; Gatersleben & Appleton, 2007; Li et al., 2013; Titze et al., 2008; Heinen et al., 2009). For instance, factor analysis by Heinen et al. (2011) revealed three underlying attitudinal factors toward cycling to work: awareness, direct trip-based benefits and safety. This indicates that, in addition to socio-economic factors, attitudes and other psychological factors have a relatively strong impact on the choice to commute by bicycle.

With regards to walking, socio-demographic differences account for much of the differences among groups of people, with evidence of higher socio-economic position and not owning a motor vehicle being positively associated with total, utilitarian, and recreational walking (Ehrenfeucht & McPherson, 2013; Riva et al., 2009; Eriksson et al., 2012). In particular, studies have shown that compared with high socio-economic status areas, low socio-economic status areas have 33% higher prevalence of walking for transport and 21% lower prevalence of walking for recreation or exercise (Giles-Corti & Donovan, 2002). Cerin et al. (2009) found that individual factors (amongst others) significantly contributed to the explanation of the relations between socio-economic status (SES) and transport-related walking frequency. Educational attainment and area- and individual-level income played independent roles in explaining frequency of walking for transport, through opposing common and distinct pathways. While engagement in leisure-time physical activity was the most influential mediator of the association between educational attainment and frequency of walking for transport, the number of motorised vehicles and perceived levels of environmental aesthetics and greenery were the strongest mediators of the relations of frequency of transport-related walking with individual- and area-level income, respectively. Dog ownership seems to be a key factor, as daily walking trips tend to be higher in households that own dogs. Hears et al. (2013) suggested that strategies to increase walking for transport or leisure need to take account of individual level socio-economic factors in addition to area-level measures.

Within a household, a number of intrapersonal- and interpersonal-level factors have been identified using mostly qualitative research. For instance, there is evidence that school travel is influenced by parent-child relationships involving factors of personal safety (largely a barrier), siblings (often a barrier), time management and motivation (Ahlport et al., 2008).

6.3.6. Factors relating to habits and life events

Prior behaviour and habits are individual factors affecting AM. To attribute the link between prior and later behaviour to habit is however problematic. Investigating the role of habit requires an indicator that is independent of past behaviour. The fast-response measure of intention (Verplanken et al., 1994) was designed to provide such an independent indicator. Its application offered little support for the mediating role of habit. Introduction of this measure had only a small effect on the direct link between prior and later use of the car, and no mediating effect at all on prediction of the behaviour that was the focus of the intervention (riding the bus to the campus). However, it would be premature to conclude that there is no role for habit in human action. Like the frequency of past behaviour, the fast-response index investigated by Verplanken et al. may not be a very good indicator of habit.

The theory of planned behaviour (see paragraph 6.4.1) also recognises elements of

automaticity/habit. Beliefs are accessed, and attitudes and intentions are consciously formulated, only in the early stages when a behaviour is new to the person. Once the behaviour has been performed many times, it is usually no longer necessary to go through a consideration of accessible beliefs. Attitudes and intentions are stored in memory, and they can be retrieved directly without much cognitive effort.

Past commuting behaviour was found to retain a significant impact on later behaviour when added to the other predictors in the theory. Past behaviour is however not always a good predictor of future behaviour. Prior behaviour is a predictor of later action only when circumstances remain relatively stable. Complex human behaviour is cognitively regulated and, even after numerous enactments, appears to be subject to at least some degree of monitoring. As a result, new information, if relevant and persuasive, can change behavioural, normative, and control beliefs; can affect intentions and perceptions of behavioural control; and can influence later behaviour. We thus conclude that human social behaviour, although it may well contain automatic elements, is based on reason.

Another individual factor to consider is life events. Chatterjee et al. (2013) investigated triggers of behaviour change. In 65 of 95 cases, changes in cycling habit occurred due to an event related to education, employment, family, residential, health or leisure factors. In 18 cases, transport related events (such as availability of a form of transport or skills to use that form of transport) triggered the change. In 8 cases a change in the external environment lead to change. The results suggest that there may be a combination of events that create a facilitating framework, responsive to a behaviour change trigger.

For example, a change in residential location could be the turning point, but the change can be motivated by the desire to live in a place where cycling is more feasible (e.g. the interdependency described in Rashidi et al., 2011)). A recent investigation by Clark et al. (2014) investigated life events as triggers for behavioural change, using data from the UK Household Longitudinal Study (UKHLS), linked to local spatial data, and confirm that urbanising and ruralising moves have contrasting effects on travel behaviour, and that travel behaviour events are more likely to occur around the time of a life event. It has previously been shown that car ownership and commuting behaviour changes significantly more for individuals who change employer or move home (Dargay and Hanly, 2007).

Summary, areas for future research

Demographic, socio-economic and vehicle access factors have long been included as the mainstay in theoretical and analytical models of explaining why and how people travel, including for active mobility and recreational walking and cycling. More recently, the inclusion of socio-psychological factors (Heinen et al., 2011) and segmentation of the population according to attitudes, preferences and habits (Li et al., 2013; Anable, 2005) have improved our understanding of (active) mobility behaviour, but gaps remain on the relative strength of the approaches, the possible dimensions of cycling attitudes, preferences and habits and about the formation of these factors. For instance, in Heinen et al. (2009), it is argued that evidence for the relationship between cycling, age and income is mixed because (a) most of the research simply uses survey results to draw links between socio-economic factors and cycling; (b) the research tends not to examine whether these are causal relationships, meaning that we are unable to draw any conclusions in this respect; and (c) large differences exist between different countries, perhaps due to the impact of differences

in countries' social and built environments, and economic circumstances. Based on these findings, Heinen et al. (2009) suggest that future research should avoid focusing too heavily on socio-economic factors, because “the relationship between certain socio-economic factors and cycling mainly results from other non-tested factors”. This is indicated, for example, by the significant differences between countries. Social values and attitudes may play a key role in this respect.

6.4. Behavioural theories

This section looks at theories of active mobility and physical activity behaviour.

6.4.1. The theory of planned behaviour

According to the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), human action is guided by three kinds of belief:

- Beliefs about the likely consequences of the behaviour (behavioural beliefs) → produce a favourable or unfavourable attitude toward the behaviour, attitude towards behaviour.
- Beliefs about the normative expectations of others (normative beliefs) → result in perceived social pressure or subjective norm.
- Beliefs about the presence of factors that may further or hinder performance of the behaviour (control beliefs) → give rise to perceived behavioural control, the perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour.

In combination, attitude toward the behaviour, subjective norm, and perception of behavioural control lead to the formation of a behavioural intention. As a general rule, the more favourable the attitude and subjective norm, and the greater the perceived control, the stronger should be the person's intention to perform the behaviour in question. Intention is thus assumed to be the immediate antecedent of behaviour.

To the extent that people are realistic regarding a behaviour's difficulty, a measure of perceived behavioural control can serve as a proxy for actual control and can contribute to the prediction of the behaviour in question (see Ajzen, 1991).

According to TPB, it should be possible to influence intentions and behaviour by designing an intervention that has significant effects on one or more of the antecedent factors, that is, on attitudes toward the behaviour, subjective norms, and perceptions of behavioural control. The results of a study by Bamberg et al. demonstrate the utility of TPB as a conceptual framework for predicting travel mode choice and for understanding the effects of an intervention on this behaviour. Attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control were found to influence students' intentions to take the bus to the campus, and these intentions in turn permitted quite accurate prediction of reported behaviour (Bamberg et al., 2003).

The theory of planned behaviour and active mobility

There is a growing interest in theoretical studies integrating cognitions and environmental variables in the prediction of AM behaviour. This approach was adopted in a study with reference to the theory of planned behaviour (Lemieux, Godin, 2009). The purpose of the

study was to gain information on the determinants of active commuting among students. Frequency of active commuting during the past four weeks was obtained. In addition, the habit of using active commuting was measured in reference to the index of Verplanken and Orbell (Verplanken, Orbell, 2006). This scale includes twelve questions related to frequency, automaticity and self-identity. The results showed that intention and habit were significant predictors of active commuting. None of the environmental variables contributed to this prediction. The most important factor influencing AM was habit. People who are in the habit of using active commuting do so more often.

Given that intention was a significant determinant of behaviour among students, it can be used to guide the development of interventions for this group. In this regard, perceived behavioural control, attitude and habit deserve special attention. Perceived behavioural control was found to be the most important determinant of intention. Also, attitude was another factor positively associated with the intention to use active commuting among in this study indicating that someone with a positive outlook towards active commuting is more inclined to use it.

The results showed that cognitive variables play a more important role than environmental variables in predicting and explaining active commuting. When environmental variables were significant, they were mediated by cognitive variables. Therefore, individual cognitions should remain one of the main focuses of interventions promoting active commuting among undergraduate and graduate students.

6.4.2. Stages of change

Typically, assessments of the effects of walking or cycling is often measured through self-reported number of trips, proportion of total travel behaviour etc. An alternative approach is to use a stage of change analysis, which can overcome some of the limitations associated with these approaches, and can even contribute to better intervention design.

One of the fundamental difficulties of intervention studies is that they are typically constrained by limited timelines. Changes in actual behaviours may take a long time, as individuals may go through a cycle of contemplation and preparation before acting upon a behavioural change. For example in the recent iCONNECT study by Goodman et al. (2014), provision of new walking and cycling infrastructure is shown to have little effect on physical activity levels of local residents after one year, but a repeated questionnaire at two years shows significant physical activity level increase. Reactions to measures can take time.

Rather than approaching behaviour change as a binary process, a more subtle approach to assessing the impacts of policies would consider changes in behaviour as a process, rather than as an event. These concepts are especially useful for policy and planning interventions, as the evidence seems to point to people in different stages of change requiring a different message or support to move on to the next stage.

Understanding of behaviour change as a dynamic process with several stages is not new. In 1944 the psychologist Kurt Lewin identified a model whereby individuals are understood to first pass through a motivational stage of intention setting followed by a volitional stage of intention striving, where skills and strategies are developed. This approach has been adopted and developed by many subsequent studies. For example in the Health Action Process Approach (HAPA) social-cognition model of health behaviour, by Schwarzer et al.

(2003). The HAPA subdivides the volitional stage into sub-processes of initiation, maintenance and recovery. The HAPA model notably identifies self-efficacy as the most influential motivational factor and predictor of behavioural intentions for the motivational phase, and a key determinant of success in the volitional stage.

Other stage models include the Precaution Adoption Process Model (Weinstein et al., 2008) and the Model of Action Phases (Gollwitzer, 1990). The diversity and range of stage models shows that categorisation of boundaries and appropriate stages can be adjusted or developed to suit the context. Overall, there are found to be four common elements of each of the stage theories, as proposed by Weinstein et al. (1998). Each stage theory is seen to have a category system to define the different stages, and an ordering of the stages (although most recognise that transition between stages can be bi-directional, and rapid progression by an individual may occasionally skip a stage). In addition, stage theories state that there are common barriers to change that will affect people who are in the same stage, and conversely that people in different stages will be affected by different barriers (or to a different degree).

6.4.3. The transtheoretical model

Many recent stage models are variations of the transtheoretical model (TTM), which has dominated other stage theories due to its wide applicability: the TTM now has a robust history of empirical application across a range of behaviours. The theoretical basis for this stage of change approach to behaviour change mainly stems from Prochaska and DiClemente's 1984 work, which conceptualises behavioural change as a transition through five stages: 1) pre-contemplation (no intention to take any action); 2) contemplation (developing awareness that a change may be necessary); 3) preparation (the intention is formed to take specific action in the near future); 4) action (actual behaviour change); 5) maintenance (working to prevent relapse) (Prochaska et al., 1997).

The TTM has been used in a number of contexts regarding physical activity. Categorisation of individuals by stage of change can be used to describe populations and to measure success of an intervention. Moreover, use of the TTM stages to tailor interventions according to stage membership has been shown to be particularly effective. The stage tailored approach has been demonstrated to improve the success of physical activity interventions in a group of women with elevated blood pressure (Daley et al., 2009); in patients with coronary heart disease (Zhu et al., 2014); and for groups of adolescents (Nigg and Courneya, 1998) amongst others.

The TTM has also been used to frame and structure more descriptive investigations into psycho-social factors and barriers associated with different stages of change, for example to investigate the context of physical activity levels in Saudi Arabia (Al-Otaibi, 2013). Hildebrand and Neufeld (2009) have also demonstrated that tailoring messaging according to the TTM stages of change was able to increase the recruitment of voluntary participants in a physical activity program that targeted older adults. Overall, it is clear that the applicability of the TTM to physical activity interventions for health outcomes is relatively well understood, and the success of tailoring interventions according to stage has been demonstrated across a range of contexts.

Mutrie et al. (2002) were one of the first to apply a transtheoretical framework to active commuting, namely implementing and evaluating a walk to work promotion intervention

through a randomised controlled trial. The stage changes were defined as:

- **Pre-contemplation:** no intention to become more active in the next 6 months.
- **Contemplation:** thinking about becoming more active in commuting within the next 6 months.
- **Preparation:** having a plan of action such as buying a bike, or having attempted some active commuting, but not enough to meet 30 minutes on most days of the week.
- **Action:** have become a regular active commuter, but only during the previous 6 months or less.
- **Maintenance:** have achieved regular active commuting for longer than 6 months.

Only subjects who were in contemplation or preparation stage for active commuting were recruited, and these were randomly assigned to the intervention or control group. A significantly larger percentage of the intervention group progressed to higher stages of active commuting (49 versus 31%) with an average difference of 18%. Factors around distance to work, age and gender did not seem to have an effect on this progression. In this study, only walking was successful and significantly different between groups; cycling was not.

Van Bekkum et al. (2011) used the same stages of change as in Mutrie (2002), but added the category: “I am a seasonal cyclist” (although this was excluded from analysis), and assessed how the perceived barriers varied according to stage of change. By stage of change, the most significant barriers were as follows:

- **Respondents in pre-contemplation:** danger on the roads, bad weather and darkness.
- **Respondents in contemplation, preparation and action:** danger on the road, bad weather and natural terrain.
- **Respondents in maintenance:** danger on the road, bad weather and manmade terrain.

Overall the most significant differences between stages of change were seen around danger on the roads, physical effort and natural terrain. Interestingly, while all respondents worked in the same (cycle friendly) workplace, their perceptions were still different.

A recent study by Driller, Thigpen and Handy (2014) uses the TTM approach to cycling commuting in UC Davis Campus. The environment is very cycle-friendly: 55% of individuals living in Davis or in campus commute by cycling and the city boasts over 100 miles of cycling paths in an area of roughly 10 square miles (26 km²). A total of 2,439 individuals are divided into five stages of change based in the answers to four survey questions related to: frequency of cycling, main mode to commute to campus, willingness to cycle to campus and intention to cycle to campus in the next 6 months. Results show the explanatory variables most related to each stage, and the hypothetical effect of different kinds of policy interventions is measured for pre-contemplation individuals. Of all the interventions, the most effective intervention in moving individuals out of pre-contemplation stage is “Access to a bicycle”, but none of the interventions manages to take individuals to the Action stage, let alone Maintenance. However cumulative effects of policy intervention scenarios on the probabilities of hypothetical individuals’ membership in each stage do take the individuals to Maintenance, with a minimum of four interventions needed. Even though this is a cross-

sectional study in a cycle-friendly community, and that the policy scenarios are hypothetical, the results suggest important aspects of stage of change in relation to policy interventions. One is that cumulative packages of intervention policies has a high probability of moving individuals to the Maintenance stage. Findings are also consistent with previous studies (Gatersleben et al., 2007) suggesting that attitudes toward bicycling and perception of barriers are important determinants of stage of change.

Though widely used, the TTM is not without criticism. The TTM recognises that behaviour change is a continuous, often cyclical process, with different characteristics associated with different stages. However by defining the stages of change, the model necessarily introduces boundaries between stages. As such, the model has been critiqued for its simplification of complex processes, and for boundary definitions that do not take full account of underpinning psychological processes (e.g. Adams and White, 2005). However meta-analysis of the TTM's application to physical activity and exercise behaviours (Marshall and Biddle, 2001) shows that in this context there are observable differences in behaviour even between pre-contemplation and contemplation stages, suggesting that the characterisation of distinct stages is indeed useful. Taken together, the studies in this chapter demonstrate the applicability of the TTM to active mobility, and the evident differences between stages of change indicates that stage tailored interventions could be particularly effective.

Self-efficacy and decision balance

Of the TTM constructs, self-efficacy and decision balance are found to be particularly influential. Self-efficacy is closely related to perceived behavioural control, and is consistently found to be the most important single determinant at an individual level. It appears to be highly relevant at every stage of change, with indicators of self-efficacy in the targeted behaviour increasing with stage progression.

The decision balance is also influential across the different stages, although the mode of influence changes with stage progression, with a meta-analysis by Hall and Rossi (2008) suggesting that decisional balance tends to have the strongest relationship with the earlier stages of change

Summary, areas for future research

The stages of change approach to describing, understanding and targeting behaviour change shows particular strengths. Categorisation of participants and measurements of progression through the stages can offer a more nuanced interpretation of an intervention's impact. Tailoring of physical activity interventions according to an individual's stage of behaviour change has been demonstrated to significantly improve results relative to control groups.

While application of the TTM in the context of active mobility and commuting behaviour is relatively new, early studies suggest that very different barriers and behavioural determinants dominate the different stages of change. This suggests that interventions targeting specific barriers or behavioural determinants will be more impactful than generic interventions, and much more likely to facilitate progression through the stages of change. Better understanding of populations' stages of change will also allow greater insight into how non-intervention factors trigger behavioural changes (such as moving home) and could allow

targeted interventions at crucial points where behaviour change is likely.

Longitudinal analyses are needed to assess if the change of stages generated by interventions is stable in the medium and longer term. It is also important to take into account that the papers mentioned in this section are related to physical activity behaviour, and see it as a mixture of diverse behaviours, active mobility within them. In this way, a better assessment of the TTM constructs for this particular behaviour is needed.

Nigg et al. (2011) consider intervention evaluation as a critical component and even propose a framework for it: the Reach, Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation and Maintenance (RE-AIM) framework. This paper also states the need to empirically test whether TTM-tailored interventions outperform non-tailored approaches, which should be a consideration for future research.

Future research should also investigate how to measure the role of habit, and the effects of habit and past behaviour on AM levels. More reliable tools standardizing the definitions of social environmental variables should be developed.

6.5. Summary of factors

There are many factors that affect levels of active mobility, and the relationships between factors is complex. Although we have tried to group factors into different categories, it is clear that when we delve into more detail that it is seldom possible to isolate individual factors and how they affect levels of active mobility as the factors are inter-linked. This has been pointed out by previous authors (e.g. Ogilvie et al., 2004; de Nazelle et al., 2011). It is also clear (see summary of factors in 5) that factors related to cycling are much more commonly researched than factors related to walking.

This relates back to the socio-ecological model introduced in section 6.2 which shows that successful measures to increase physical activity, or in our case active mobility, should focus on several different strands: the individual, social environment, physical environment and policy. This has further been taken up in the PASTA framework. The review shows that successful measures to increase active mobility must focus on all of these aspects, and at the same be implemented in broad schemes – “a multi-pronged approach”.

Table 5 Overview of factors that affect active mobility from the literature review

Factor	Category	Direction of influence	Other comments	Reference
Policies to increase walking and cycling	Policies	Lack proper evaluation most cases. Bias towards small easily evaluated samples of motivated volunteers with positive effect of measure.	Multi-pronged strategies are most effective at creating change is suggested, but difficult to prove.	de Nazelle et al., 2011; Pucher et al., 2010; Yang et al., 2010; Scheepers et al., 2014; Krizek et al. 2009
Design of urban environment	Physical environment	The way that the environment is designed impacts on levels of active mobility.		Sallis et al., 2012; Aldred & Woodcock, 2008
Residential densities	Physical environment	Several studies point to higher densities having higher levels of cycling.	One study shows converse in the review.	In review Heinen et al., 2010
Mixed land use	Physical environment	Mixed land use leads to higher levels of cycling mode choice.		In review Heinen et al., 2010
Bikeability	Physical environment	High bikeability related to higher levels of cycling and physical activity.		Pucher et al., 2010 / Browne et al., 2013
Walkability	Physical environment	High walkability related to higher levels of walking and physical activity.		Eriksson et al., 2013
Infrastructure, street connectivity, facility provision	Physical environment	Cycling infrastructure, street connectivity and facility provision lead to higher levels of cycling.	What counts as 'good' infrastructure for cycling varies for individuals. It is not necessarily bad infrastructure that puts people off active mobility (Nkurunziza et al. 2012). Heinen et al's review (2010) does not come to a definitive conclusion regarding this relationship.	Panter & Jones, 2010; Molina-García et al., 2010; Titze et al., 2008; Owen et al., 2004 ; Heinen et al., 2010; iConnect study
Slope	Physical environment	Hilliness is negatively affected with levels of cycling.		Heinen et al., 2010
Weather	Physical environment	Bad weather related to lower levels of cycling.	Bad weather refers to (probable) rain, cold and darkness. Note that weather is not the same as climate!	Heinen et al., 2010
Travel time / distance	Physical environment / individual	Low travel time and short distances related to higher levels of cycling.		Heinen et al., 2010
Effort	Physical environment / individual	Less (physical) effort for cycling related to higher levels of cycling.	Effort is individual and also varies between men and women	Heinen et al., 2010
Perceived safety	Social environment / individual	Higher perceived (or 'subjective') safety, higher levels of active mobility.		Noland, 1995; Ogilvie, Egan et al., 2004; Carver, Salmon et al., 2005; Hoehner, Brennan Ramirez et al., 2005; Kerr, Rosenberg et al., 2006; Jacobsen, Racioppi et al., 2009; Reynolds, Harris et al., 2009; Nelson and Woods, 2010; Winters and Teschke, 2010; Heinen, Maat et al., 2011; Van Dyck, Cerin et al., 2012; Morckel and Terzano, 2014; Sanders, 2015

Safety	Physical environment / Social environment / individual	Higher levels of (objective) safety related to higher levels of cycling.		Heinen et al., 2010
(Motorised) traffic speeds	Physical environment	Increased speeds associated with less safety.	Empirical evidence is rare. Safety related to levels of active mobility.	Elvik, 2009; Strauss, Miranda-Moreno et al., 2013; Strauss, Miranda-Moreno et al., 2014
Higher volume vehicles	Physical environment	Higher volume of vehicles (both motorised and non-) associated with more safety at junctions.	USA one site study.	Nordback et al. (2014)
Traffic calming	Physical environment	Traffic calming (for motorised vehicles) associated with higher safety.		Bunn et al. (2003)
Cycle tracks	Physical environment	Cycle tracks associated with higher safety (than cycling with mixed traffic).	Collisions higher on roads, falls and injuries (single accidents) higher on cycle tracks.	Reynolds et al. (2009); Teschke et al., 2012; Lusk et al. (2011); Aultman-Hall and Kaltenecker (1999)
Large vehicles	Physical environment	Large vehicles (HGVs) associated with reduced safety for cycling.		Morgan, Dale et al., 2010
Compulsory bicycle helmets	Social environment	Compulsory helmet laws lead to reductions in levels of cycling.	Compulsory helmet laws lead to lower levels of cycling. With regards safety: evidence on preventive effects of helmet laws is insufficient to weigh injury prevention effects against unintended public health consequences from less people cycling.	Grant and Rutner, 2004; Robinson, 2006; De Jong, 2012; Fyhri, Bjørnskau et al., 2012
Safety in numbers	Social environment	Higher levels of cycling means safer cycling OR safer cycling leads to higher numbers of cyclists.		Jacobsen, 2003; Elvik, 2009
Social norm	Social environment	Social norms impact whether a person will cycle or not.		Bamberg et al., 2011; Blöbaum 2007; Xing et al 2010
Normalisation of active mobility	Social environment	Infrastructure measures such as bike share scheme can contribute to “normalising” cycling for individuals who have previous viewed cycling as not the norm		Goodman et al, 2014; Ogilvie et al, 2016
Social support	Social environment	What your family or close friends think about cycling impacts whether you cycle or not	Who is included in the close social network depends on different cultures/geographies	Muñoz et al, 2013; Geus et al 2008
Socio-economic factors generally	Individual	“There is a relationship between socio-economic factors and cycling to/from work, but we lack clarity on both the direction of this relationship, and its causality.”	In addition to socio-economic factors, attitudes and other psychological factors have a relatively strong impact on the choice to commute by bicycle.	Heinen et al., 2011
Age, seniors	Individual	Seniors associated with higher levels of walking.	Difference in different socio-demographic and economic profiles	Moniruzzaman et al., 2013
Age, children	Individual	Children associated with higher levels of active mobility.	Along with insufficient household income, having an older sibling, and living in a neighbourhood that is not excellent for raising children, or characterized with high decay, higher levels of AM. Increasing household	Pabayo et al., 2013; Mackett, 2013; McDonald, 2012

			income and increasing car ownership, lower levels AM.	
No access to car	Individual	Lack of car access associated with increased levels of active mobility	For younger people. Studies from UK. Study from Spain related to active commuting.	Panter et al., 2013; Adams, 2010; Molina-García et al., 2010
Car ownership	Individual	No car or fewer cars leads to more cycling.		See review Heinen et al., 2010
Physical ability	Individual	Ability to undertake physical activity associated with higher levels of cycling.		Handy et al., 2010
Ethnic groups	Individual	In some cases ethnic groups associated with higher or lower levels of AM. The direction is largely context specific		Pont et al., 2009
Lower income	Individual	Lower income associated with higher levels of AM.		McDonald, 2008
Higher income	Individual	Higher income professionals associated with higher levels of cycle commuting.		Dill & Gliebe, 2008
Higher socioeconomic position and not owning a motor vehicle	Individual	+ walking		Ehrenfeucht & McPherson, 2013; Riva et al., 2009; Eriksson et al., 2012
Low socio-economic status areas	Individual	+ walking	Higher prevalence walking for transport but lower prevalence of walking for recreation or exercise.	Giles-Corti & Donovan, 2002
Educational level	Individual	+ walking	Most important mediator: engagement in leisure-time physical activity.	Cerin et al., 2009
Area- and individual-level income	Individual	+ walking	Most important mediators: number of motorised vehicles and perceived levels of environmental aesthetics and greenery.	Cerin et al., 2009
Dog ownership	Individual	+ walking		Hearst et al., 2013
Costs of other modes	Individual	Higher costs of other modes of transport leads to higher levels of AM.	e.g. parking fees, fuel taxes, road user charges as well as financial incentives such as free parking or subsidized public transport tickets.	Buehler, 2012; Handy & Xing, 2010; Handy et al., 2010

7. Summary and concluding remarks

In a nutshell, this report looked at what active mobility (AM) is, what can be done to increase active mobility, and what factors affect active mobility.

What is active mobility?

Active mobility (AM) is defined in this report as regular physical activity undertaken as a means of transport. It includes travel by foot, bicycle and other vehicles which require physical effort to get moving. Use of public transport is also included in the definition as it often involves some walking or cycling to pick-up and from drop-off points. It does not include walking, cycling or other physical activity that is undertaken for recreation.

This definition has been developed based on the work done in the PASTA project, but it is important to note that the field of AM is relatively new, and multi-disciplinary. Different terminology is common, as well as different interpretations of active mobility.

What can be done to increase active mobility?

Active mobility measures (AMM) are actions undertaken in order to increase the level of active mobility (in a specified population). This ranges from changing urban infrastructure or introducing new policies to campaigns to change people's transport behaviour. This report has developed a categorisation of AMM based on previous classifications, which classifies measures in four categories: strategic policy, social environment, physical environment and regulation and legislation. These categories can be applied to different modes: walking, cycling, public transport, and other.

Active mobility measures are however, often difficult to pin down into specific categories, often existing in overlapping categories. This is also partly because active mobility measures are most effective if they are implemented together.

What factors affect active mobility?

There are many factors that affect active mobility, and the relationship between factors is complex. We have categorised these factors following the PASTA framework, focusing on: policies, physical environment, social environment, individual factors, behavioural theories, and social environment factors. Although we have tried to group factors into different categories, it is clear that when we delve into more detail that it is seldom possible to isolate individual factors and how they affect levels of active mobility as the factors are inter-linked. The review shows that successful measures to increase active mobility must focus on all of these aspects, and at the same be implemented in broad schemes – “a multi-pronged approach”.

Concluding remarks

Active mobility is a new field that crosses different disciplines. Increasing levels of AM is a good way to increase levels of physical activity, but there needs to be a joint understanding by professionals from different disciplines as to what AM is, and what needs to be done to increase levels of AM. Active mobility measures are best implemented in packages of measures, rather than as single measures, and should include input from both health and transport fields in their design. Additionally, since there are many factors that impact active mobility measures, the design of the measures needs to take into account local conditions,

thus description of measures should include variables on the context in which they were implemented, in order to be able to enhance their transferability.

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Annex Searching and recording

SEARCHING AND RECORDING 1A-B

Overview

This document includes practical instructions in order to perform literature reviews to answer questions 1A and 1B according to the search strategy.

This document contains information on:

1. Sources to be searched by partner
2. How to perform the search
3. Recording of searches and results
4. File handling

1. Sources to be searched by partner

Partner	Searches			Where to look	Time period
BOKU	1A	1 B	2	Electronic Journal Library EZB BOKU:Lit search Transportation Research Record	2000-present 2000-present 2007-present
UZH	1A	1 B	2	Pubmed Google Scholar	2007-present 2000-present
VITO	1A	1 B	2	Transportation Research Record ScienceDirect (research fields not relevant for public health & epidemiology: <i>Arts and Humanities; Business, Management and Accounting; Chemical Engineering; Chemistry; Computer Science; Decision Science; Earth, Planetary Sciences; Economics, Econometrics and Finance; Energy; Engineering; Environmental Science; Material Science; Mathematics; Physics and Astronomy; Social Sciences</i>)	2000-2006 2000-present
CREAL	1A	1 B	2	ScienceDirect (public health & epidemiology journals, compare with VITO) Scopus (public health & epidemiology journals) The Cochrane Library	2000-present 2000-present 2000-2006
LBN	1A	1 B		Normal Google Known databases (UK, transport)	2000-2006 2000-present
RSM	1A	1 B		Normal Google Known databases (transport)	2007-present 2000-present
WHO	1A			WHO European Database on Nutrition, Obesity and Physical Activity (NOPA) THE PEP Clearing House THE PEP toolbox Health Systems Evidence SAFETY LIT STEPS	2000-present for all
UOXF			2	ScienceDirect Web of Science Social Science & Geography Journals (such as Environment and Planning A)	2000-present for all
DSHS			2	SPORTDiscus MedPilot	2000-present for all

POLIS	1A	1 B	Intelligent Energy-Europe IEE FP7 Eltis EPOMM Transport Research and Innovation Portal (TRIP) LIFE programme EU projects: (Active Travel Network project, SEGMENT, CIVITAS, SUMP portal, ENDURANCE, Stepping Stones)	2000-present for all
GÖG	1A	1 B	Pubmed The Cochrane library	

2. How to perform the search

In performing and recording a search, the following steps apply (this is demonstrated in the image below):

- Perform search in stated sources according to the search criteria given for the question.
- Log the search performed in the Excel template.
- Screen/look at each article.
- If the article is relevant to answer the question, save the file in the appropriate folder in Google Drive. Record the result in the appropriate Excel template.
- If the article is relevant to answer question 1b, record the result in the appropriate Excel template (search 1b).
- (Optional) If the article is relevant to answer another question, a note can be made of this.
- Continue screening articles as long as you get new results.

Figure A1. Flow chart for the literature searches 1A and 1B.

2.1 Practical considerations

Not a fully comprehensive review

The literature review is not intended to be a fully comprehensive review. Based on the limited timeframe in order to deliver preliminary results to other work packages, the literature review is part of a Rapid Evidence Assessment (REA). In accordance with the REA methodology, the findings from the review will be combined with input from experts and practitioners at workshops within WP1. Although a fully comprehensive review won't be executed, this review, following the REA methodology, will be transparent, robust and as comprehensive as possible with respect to the given timeframe for the review.

Stop screening when the number of relevant articles drops

As the literature review according to the REA methodology aims at providing a breadth rather than comprehensive depth, the screening of results in each search should stop when new articles don't seem to provide any further terms or definitions. As the number of relevant results differ between sources and search strings, a fixed number for when to stop screening articles would be hard to apply. Rather, if the last 5-10 screenings of articles don't seem to add new definitions to record, the screening may be stopped.

This approach is in line with "purposive searches" in the REA method. As the aim is to build

a ‘mosaic’ of different perspectives and views on definitions and usage of terms, the screening of results may be stopped if additional screening of studies don’t seem to add any more detail to the mosaic.

Searches may be further delimited to lower the number of search results (hits)

It is not the objective to have a fully comprehensive review, but to have an overview of different fields and disciplines. In some databases and for certain searches, there may be a high number of irrelevant hits. In order to limit results further, we leave it to the discretion of those who perform the searches. Any changes / further delimitations included must be written up in the Excel sheet. Further delimitations may be: a) searching for review articles only; b) searching only within certain research fields; c) searching only in the title of articles.

Register each relevant article only once

Each article only needs to be registered once. Register the article/hit as belonging to the search where it was first encountered.

How to handle recommended articles and references to articles

In this search, we only screen and register articles in the results list of each search. If preferred, article recommendations and references to articles within a screened article may be saved and registered for possible later use. In that case, use “XXX” as result ID in the file name and upload the article to Google Drive. For example an article by Thomas Anderson that is referenced in an article screened during search number 4 may be saved as: “1A-BOKU-04-XXX-Anderson-T-2004”. General meta data may also, if preferred, be recorded in the Excel template together with a comment on the possible relevance of the article. The data may be registered either in the same work sheet in Excel or in a new work sheet.

2.2 Search strings

The following search strings should be used to answer each research question (see table below). For some questions, only one search is needed in each database. For other, several search strings should be applied to each database.

Search	Table text	
1A.I*	Terms used for “active transport”	<pre>"physical activity" AND ("transport*" OR "travel" OR "mobility") AND ("walk*" OR "cycl*" OR "bik*") NOT ("membrane" OR "cell*" OR "chromosome walking" OR "substrate cycling")</pre>
1A.II	What is meant by terms we consider using for “active transport”?	<pre>"active transport" "active mobility" "active transportation" "active travel"</pre>
1A.III*	Terms used for “active transport measure”	<pre>("increas*" OR "support*" OR "improv*" OR "affect*") AND ("cycl*" OR "walk*" OR "bik*") AND ("transport*" OR "travel*") NOT ("membrane" OR "cell" OR "substrate cycling" OR "chromosome walking")</pre>

1A.IV	What is meant by terms we consider using for “active transport measure”?	“active transport” AND (“intervention” OR “measure”) “active mobility” AND (“intervention” OR “measure”) “active transportation” AND (“intervention” OR “measure”) “active travel” AND (“intervention” OR “measure”)
1B	Classification of active transport measures	<i>No search is performed. The research question is answered by screening the relevant results from searches 1A.</i>

*For search 1A.I and 1A.III the search strings may be elaborated in order to better match the search engine in each database and to give more relevant search results, as long as the modified search string is in line with the aim of the search in question.

Elaborating with search strings to work with each search engine

In order to provide relevant search results, and since search engines work differently, some search terms may be elaborated in order to better work with each search engine. This applies to search 1A.I (terms used for “active transport”) and 1A.III (terms used for “active transport measure”). As the search string used is recorded in the Excel template, this doesn’t affect the transparency of the research performed. Note that searches 1A.II and 1A.IV should not be elaborated, with the exception of *the syntax* if it has to be changed in order to work with a certain search engine. When elaborating with a search string, make sure that the modified search string is *in line with the aim of the search in question*. Preferably, state the rationale behind the elaboration in the comment field when recording the search in the Excel template.

Tips on handling databases

Order by relevance

In some databases, results are by default ordered chronologically rather than by relevance. You may need to manually specify that the search should be sorted by relevance as a criteria.

Searching in Google Scholar

In Google (Scholar), you need to use the following syntax in order to get accurate results:

- Use square brackets instead of round brackets
- Use | for ‘or’ without any spaces
- Use – for ‘not’ without a space
- Do not use *, google automatically looks at variants of the same word
- If you use ‘and’, write it in capitals (although it’s obsolete)

Example:

```
[support|increase|improve] [cycling|walking|biking]
[transport|travel|mobility] -membrane -cell -"substrate cycling"
-"chromosome walking"
```

Searching in ScienceDirect

Syntax “NOT” may have to be changed to “AND NOT” in search strings in order to work.

3.

Recording of searches and results

We are recording the searches to ensure that we have covered a wide range of different sources as required for the questions.

Descriptions are given below of the data fields in the Excel template. Each search, as well as all relevant results, should be recorded in the appropriate templates. There are three template work sheets in the Excel file.

Templates for recording searches:

- Recording of search 1A

Templates for recording results:

- Recording of results 1A
- Recording of interventions 1B

RECORDING OF SEARCH

1A

For each search, the following data should be recorded in the Excel template. *Each search* is recorded as a new row in the template.

Data regarding searches 1A.I, 1A.II, 1A.III and 1A.IV are recorded in the work sheet “*Recording of search 1A*”.

Field	Description
Search ID	Give <i>each</i> performed search a search ID. A first search to answer research question 1A performed by Trivector is given the ID: 1A-TRIV-01, where 1A = research question, TRIV = the partner abbreviation, 01 = the consecutive number of the search performed starting with 01. The third search performed by BOKU in order to answer research question 1A will get the search ID: 1A-BOKU-03.
Dare	Date when search was performed, DD/MM/YYYY
Search string	The search string used in search
Search part (Only for search 1A)	State the part of search A1 the search is intended to answer: I, II, III or IV (according to the search strategy).
Data source	Name of source, for example "Google", name of database or library.
Language(s)	For these research questions, searches are performed in English only. English abstracts for articles in other languages may be included.

Timespan	State the timespan applied, for example 01/01 2000 – 01/02 2014.
Other search delimitations	Are there other search delimitations (for example: limited to certain research fields, limited to reviews only, limited to title of articles only).
# of results	State the number of results (hits) given by the search.
# of screened results	State the number of results that have been screened (at least title and abstract).
# of recorded results	State the number of results that are screened as relevant and therefore have been recorded.
Comment	Other relevant information regarding the search performed, for example rationale behind modification of search string.

RECORDING OF RESULTS 1A (Definitions)

1A

Field	Description
Search ID	State the search ID that the result corresponds to (from "Recording of search").
Result ID	Give the result a consecutive number in a number series related to the search ID. For the first search performed, give the result a hit ID a consecutive number starting with 101. For search number 2, start the hit ID consecutive numbering for the first hit with 201 et cetera. The third result in the fourth search would be given the result ID: 403.
Document type	State the data source or type of document, i.e. "peer-reviewed article", "report", "conference abstract" et cetera.
Discipline	The discipline of the article, i.e. "transport", "epidemiology", "public health" etc.
Sector	State the country of research. If multiple countries, state continent, or "international" if multiple continents.
Country of research	For these research questions, searches are performed in English only. English abstracts for articles in other languages may be included.
Country of case / experiment (if applicable)	If the article describes a case/experiment, state the country where the experiment is set.
Journal / Publishing organization	State the name of the journal (scientific literature) or publishing organisation (grey literature).
Author(s)	State the authors. (This and other article metadata may be copy-pasted.)
Title	Title of article.
Year	Year of publication.

Aim / Objective	A short (1-2 sentences) description of the aim/objective/subject of the article/text. May be copied from the text.
Term used	State the term used. If multiple terms with the same definition in article, state the main term in "Term used" and synonyms in the "Synonyms" field. If multiple terms with different definitions in article, make a new row for each definition, state each term and its definition and copy the result id and meta data about the article to the new row.
Definition/meaning (if stated)	State the definition of the term used, or which meaning the term is given in the article. For example "active mobility" may simply be described as "walking or biking" or may be given a more elaborated definition.
Synonyms	State synonyms to the term mentioned in article.
Annotation / Comment (optional)	Free text.
PDF (x)	State if pdf is available on Google Drive.
Plain text / abstract (x)	State if plain text version or text abstract is available on Google Drive.
Relevant for other screenings? (optional)	If preferred, flag if the article is relevant for other screenings, such as 1B or 2.

RECORDING OF INTERVENTIONS 1B

1B

The articles screened and recorded to answer questions 1A are screened also for interventions. The results are recorded in the work sheet "*Recording of interventions 1B*".

Field	Description
Search ID	The search ID that the result corresponds to (from the tab "Recording of search 1A").
Result ID	The result ID of the article (from the tab "Recording of results 1A").
Type/term of "intervention"	Term used to describe the intervention, if any. E.g. Work place intervention / Neighbourhood renewal / Media campaign ...
Short description of intervention	Give a short description of the intervention (1-2 sentences).
Target group	Is there a stated target group? E.g. age group, gender, employees, students ...
Annotation / Comment (optional)	Free text.

4. File handling

Folder in Google Drive

Screened and recorded articles are stored in the partner folder in Google Drive:

PASTA > WP1 > LITERATURE REVIEW > 1A DEFINITIONS > [PARTNER]

File names

Articles may be saved as pdf-files or full-text/abstracts in plain text as a document. Files should be named in this format, including search ID, record id, first author and year:

[SEARCH ID]–[RECORD ID]–[FIRST AUTHOR]–[YEAR]

You get the Search ID and Record ID with their consecutive numbering from the Excel template.

For example, a pdf-file belonging to search id 1A-TRIV-03 and record id 303 written by Anderson, Bjorn in 2003 will get the file name:

1A-TRIV-03-303-Anderson-B-2003

If published by whole institution

If the article is published by a whole institution (e.g. a ministry), you may replace [FIRST AUTHOR] with the name of the institution or a suitable acronym. Explain the acronym in the comments field for the result in the Excel Template.

Annex List of performed searches

Partner	Source	Time span	Other delimitations
BOKU	Transportation Research Board	2007 – present	
BOKU	BOKU Literature Search	2000 – present	
CREAL	Science Direct	2000 – present	
CREAL	Scopus	2000 – present	
DSHS	SportDiscus	2000 – present	Some searches with slightly shorter timespan
GOEG	Cochrane Systematic Review	No timespan	
GOEG	Database of Reviews of Effects DARE	No timespan	
GOEG	NHS Economic Evaluation Database EED	No timespan	
GOEG	PubMed	2000 – 2014*	
GOEG	www.apho.org.uk	2000 – present	
GOEG	www.who.int/hia/examples/trspt_comms/en/index.html	No timespan	
LBN	Google	2000 – present	UK and PDF only** (not included)
POLIS	Intelligent Energy Europe	2008 – 2013	
RSM	Google	Various	
VITO	Transportation Research Board	2000 – 2006	
VITO	Science Direct	2000 – present	
TRIV	ELTIS		
TRIV	European Commission website		

*Timespan differs between individual searches.

+ Date search performed, search #, rationale behind modified search string, ...

Annex Examples of AMM

Name of measure	Category	Mode	City	Country	Description measure/link	Innovation aspect	Addresses health and planning (yes/no/no info)	Institutional cooperation (yes/no/no info)	Perceived positive effects	Evaluated positive effects	Transferability
Cycle Super Highway in Greater Copenhagen	Physical environment	Cycling	Copenhagen	Denmark	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/cycle-super-highway-greater-copenhagen-denmark	New cycle superhighway	no	Cooperation across neighbouring municipalities		Yes : The Albertslund route has seen a ten per cent increase in users, most of whom previously used a car or public	Notes on success factors

										transport.	
Making cycling in Bristol safer - democratically	Social environment	Cycling	Bristol	UK	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/making-cycling-bristol-safer-democratically-united-kingdom	Forming a new commission to investigate how to make cycling safer	no info	yes but details not found	yes in terms of bring stakeholders together, not in terms of increased cycling		yes
Mobility management in companies - competition	Social environment and physical environment	Cycling and public transport	Graz	Austria	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/becoming-bicycle-friendly-employer-graz-austria	Competition among employers - winner gets funds to implement measur	no info	no	Perceived to get more people cycling in a single workplace - not		yes

						es			evaluat ed		
OV Fiets	Physic al environ ment	cycling in combi nation with PT	country wide	Nether lands	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/ov-fiets-public-bicycles-netherlands	Country wide public bike scheme	no	yes across differen t levels of govern ment and betwee n public private transpo rt operato rs		number of bicycle uses known but contribu tion to shift in behavio ur not known	yes
Met Belgerin kel naar de Winkel' (in English 'with bell	Social environ ment	cycling	Flander s Region	Belgiu m	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/bell-ringing-shop-biggest-bicycle-campaign-belgium	tradition al bike campaig n to get more people cycling to	no	cooper ation betwee n munic ipalities and with		Number of shops/ municip alities / particip ants known	yes

ringing to the shop'						shops, adapted to Belgian characteristics, and with a focus on younger people		shopkeepers and cycling groups		but not shift from other mode	
Public bike rental	Physical environment	cycling	Krakow	Poland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/public-bicycle-rental-system-krakow-poland	Innovative in Poland with low cycling rates	no	no info	yes in terms of number of rented bikes.		To some extent yes, but the system was shut down after EU project funding ended
Pedelec Testing for senior	Social environment	cycling	Graz	Austria	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/pedelec-testing-senior-citizens-graz-austria	New mode of transport tested by	no info	no info	Yes - qualitative feedback was	to some extent	yes but on very small scale

citizens						target group over 1 week			good. Data on changes to trips less full		
Cycle and win	social environment	cycling	apeldoorn & eindhoven	Netherlands	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/cycle-and-win-rewards-cycling-netherlands	New promotional concept in combination with new infrastructure	no info	lack of cooperation with shopkeepers. Cooperation municipalities and Fietsbe raad		to some extent - different experience in different context. No info on mode shift but detailed information on user groups available	yes but needs careful consideration, and existence of cycle infrastructure & maybe also existing high level of cycling?

Bicycle and pedestrian bridge	Physical environment	cycling and walking	Krakow	Poland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/safe-river-crossing-pedestrians-and-cyclists-krakow-poland	Innovative in Poland where little dedicated infrastructure for cyclists and pedestrians	no info	no info	Yes - high use assumed, people stopped illegally walking over the road (motorway) bridge which was very dangerous		yes - cost is an issue
Floating walkway	Physical environment	Walking	Mechelen	Belgium	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/pedestrians-walk-water-mechelen-belgium	New walkway on water to open up new spaces and connect new	no info	yes		Yes to some extent evaluated, but part of other measures.	yes - the main point is adapting to the specifics and require

						areas for pedestrians				Winner several prizes in Flanders	ments of the areas
Cycling friends for migrant women	Social environment	Cycling	Flanders Region	Belgium	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/cycling-friends-migrant-women-belgium	Getting new groups to take up cycling	no info	yes	Yes but small group and large amount of work to achieve		Yes but small group and large amount of work to achieve
Cycle superhighways	Physical environment	Cycling	London	UK	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/londons-barclays-cycle-superhighways-uk	New large programme for cycle commuting	no info	no info		Yes	Yes

Strategic planning for cycling	Physical environment and social environment	Cycling	Leipzig	Germany	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/leipzig-triples-number-bicycle-riders-germany	Integrated longterm approach	no info	yes		From 5 - 14 % mode share cycling trips in city from 1981-2011	Yes
Around the world in 80 days	social environment	cycling	nation wide	Denmark	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/around-world-80-days-cycling-campaign-danish-schoolchildren	tackling children cycling	no info	no info		increased cycling rates over campaign period	Yes
Strategic planning for cycling	Physical environment and social environment	cycling	Lviv	Ukraine	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/zero-carbon-mobility-cycling-lviv-ukraine	application of strategic approach to cycling in very car-dominant ed	no info	yes	Yes, but no systematic evaluation?		Yes

						culture					
Workpla ce travel plans national program me	Social environ ment	cycling and walkin g	nation wide	Ireland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/engaging-employers-workplace-travel-planning-ireland	Applicati on on national level in new country	no info	yes		Yes - on average 18 % reductio n in car trips for commut ing	Yes, this also built a lot on experie nce in UK
Workpla ce cycle challeng e	Social environ ment	cycling	nation wide	New Zealan d	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/workplace-cycle-challenges-uk-australia-and-new-zealand	Applicati on in new markets / countrie s	Addres ses health outcom es	this is a private enterpri se working with public bodies		Yes	Yes - model from NZ applied in different countrie s
Newspa per campaig n for cycling	Social environ ment	cycling	nation wide	UK	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/times-newspapers-cities-fit-cycling-campaign	Initiative from major newspa per	no info / no	means to influen ce differen t groups	Yes, but no details in terms of actual		Maybe difficult to get such a focus from newspa

								rather than involve	impacts		per editors
Children's street	Regulation and legislation / social environment	cycling and walking	Brasov	Romania	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/promoting-car-free-kid-friendly-streets-brasov-romania	Target group children and closing down a street	no info	yes	yes, but no details on longterm effects		yes
Private cargo bike sharing	social environment	cycling	Ghent	Belgium	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/private-cargo-bike-sharing-ghent-belgium	Whole new concept to encourage people not to use car	no info	no info	Very small benefits / very small scale		Yes, but required support of local authority
Public cargo bike sharing	Social environment and physical environment	cycling	Ghent	Belgium	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/public-cargo-bike-sharing-ghent-belgium	Whole new concept linked to car-sharing company	no info	yes	Very small benefits / very small scale		Yes, but required support car-sharing company and

	ment					y					business model
Cycling exam for children	Social environment	cycling	nation wide	Flanders / Belgium	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/great-cycling-exam-regional-real-traffic-cycling-exam-flanders-belgium	New concept at national level	no info / link to safety	yes	improved safety		yes
Company bikes instead of cars	Social environment	cycling	Turku	Finland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/promoting-cycling-over-company-cars-turku-finland	social media campaign; bikes pimped by local artists	no info	no info	yes		yes
Cycle school for adults	Social environment	cycling	Leuven	Belgium	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/cycling-school-leuven-belgium	not really innovative	no info	yes	yes		yes- been applied many places

Cycle training immigrants	Social environment	cycling	Linköping	Sweden	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/increased-cycling-and-richer-everyday-life-lindkoping-sweden	not really innovative	no info	yes	yes	Popular and consistent number participants over 5 years	yes - been applied many places
Friday cycling campaign	social environment	cycling	Gdansk	Poland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/friday-cycling-campaign-gdansk-poland	cycle promotion where cycling is low	no info	info	yes		yes - as long as campaign adapted to local circumstances
Shop by bike	social environment	cycling	nation wide	UK	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/shop-bike-campaign-united-kingdom	targeting leisure cyclists to use bike for utility purposes	no info	no info	yes	to some extent	yes - as long as campaign adapted to local circumstances

New cycling bridge / infrastructure	physical environment	cycling	Eindhoven	Netherlands	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/floating-roundabout-cyclists-eindhoven-netherlands	New way to get cyclists across busy junction - large cycle flows	no info	no info		cycle counts	yes if relevant (but expensive, and probably would need high cycle flows)
Broad bicycle campaign	social environment	cycling	Munich	Germany	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/munich-cycle-capital-campaign-germany	Broad approach / large cost	no info	no info		In 2002 Munich had approximately a 10% bicycle share in the modal split. In 2012 it is 17%. Not sure how much related to this	yes

										campaign, but evaluation has been performed	
Go Barrhead! School Cycling Initiative	social environment	cycling	East Renfrewshire	Scotland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/go-barrhead-schools-cycling-initiative-east-renfrewshire-scotland	several new ways to involve school children include introducing cycling to school curriculum	yes	no info		yes	yes
Park and bike terminal	physical environment	cycling	Aarhus	Denmark	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/denmarks-first-park-and-bike-terminal-aarhus	new to Denmark	no info	no info	yes		yes already been applied in other places

Fillaristit map based community website	social environment	cycling	nation wide	Finland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/fillaristit-map-based-community-website-links-cyclists-together-finland	new way to get input / involvement of cyclists	no	yes	yes, but unsure about how the info is used, or if it's just a promotional tool		Yes
Mobimart - shift from car to Bicycle	social environment	cycling	Bologna	Italy	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/incentivising-shift-more-cycling-bologna-italy	Mobility credits	no - focus on CO2	no info		not great impact but probably due to rainy weather ?	Yes
segmented campaign new inhabitants	social environment	cycling	Utrecht	Netherlands	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/segmented-campaign-increase-cycling-new-inhabitants-utrecht-netherlands	segmentation to new inhabitants	no info	no info		yes	yes

Free bike rental	physical environment	cycling	Cervia	Italy	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/get-around-easily-free-bike-rental-cervia-it	application to tourist town / new in Cervia	no info	no info		yes - but no info on mode shift	yes
Pedestrian safety crossing	physical environment	walking	Gdansk	Poland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/improving-safety-pedestrian-crossings-gdansk-poland	new application to Poland	no	no info	yes		yes
Ciclo cultura	social environment	cycling	Naples	Italy	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/ciclo-cultura-event-encourage-citizens-use-bicycles-casalnuovo-di-napoli-italy	new to Naples	no info	no info	yes but small scale - no mode shift		yes
New pathway for active modes	physical environment	cycling and walking	Helsinki	Finland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/new-pathway-pedestrians-and-cyclists-helsinki-finland	new to Helsinki	no info	no info		yes - in cyclist counts	yes

Public bike scheme	physical environment	Cycling	Warsaw	Poland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/veturilo-warsaws-public-bicycle-rental-scheme-poland	new to Warsaw with very little cycling	no info	no info		number of use - assumed contribution to modal shift. Not sure if evaluated	yes - bike share all over the place!
Bike parking	physical environment	Cycling	Tirgu Mures	Romania	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/muresonbike-parking-spaces-bikes-and-pro-cycling-movement-tirgu-mures-romania	new to Tirgu Mures	no info	no info	yes - in combination with cycling "critical mass"		yes
Campus bikeshare	Physical environment and social environment	Cycling	Cork	Ireland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/promoting-cycling-university-college-cork-ireland	Adapted bike share to local circumstances	no info	no info		yes - in combination with other measures	yes - suitable for large employers

Bike marketing	Social environment	Cycling	Bolzano	Italy	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/bike-mobility-bolzano-bozen	New broad campaign / marketing of cycling	no info	no info		Yes	Yes - see Trendytravel project
Bike services for students	Social environment	Cycling	Ghent	Belgium	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/bike-service-students-student-and-mobility-city-ghent-belgium	Specific target group	no info	no info		Yes - bike counts only	Yes
No ridiculous car trips	Social environment	Cycling	Malmö	Sweden	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/no-ridiculous-car-trips-malmo-sweden	Carefully thought out based on data from travel survey	no info	no info		Yes	Yes
Legible London wayfinding system	Physical environment	Walking	London	UK	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/wayfinding-system-pedestrians-london-uk	Very carefully designed wayfinding system	no info	no info		Yes	Yes

						based on research and market research					
cycle training primary schools	Social environment	cycling	Maribor	Slovenia	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/cycling-training-primary-school-pupils-maribor-slovenia	new approach to cycle training and linking to other events	yes	yes		Yes in terms of number of participants	Yes
Cycle training young people	Social environment	cycling	Varna	Bulgaria	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/cycle-training-young-people-varna-bulgaria	new approach in place with low cycling levels	no info	no info	yes - number of people reached rather than change in behaviour		Yes

Financial support MM in schools	Social environment	All	Graz	Austria	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/supporting-mobility-management-schools-graz-austria	catalogue of measures / financial support from LA	yes	yes	yes		Yes
Green wave for pedestrians	physical environment	walking	Graz	Austria	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/green-wave-increases-safety-and-reduces-waiting-time-graz-cyclists-and	testing new technology	no	no info	Yes but not from motorists - the signal was removed!		Yes
MM for employer	social environment	all	Dublin	Ireland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/mobility-management-childrens-university-hospital-temple-st-dublin-ireland	new to employer	no info / but implemented in health care facility	no info		Yes	Yes

Bici/pedi bus	social environment	walking and cycling	Reggio Emilia Romagna	Italy	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/greener-ways-travelling-school-reggio-emilia-italy	implemented on a wide scale with same concept, central organisation	no info	yes		Yes	Yes
Bike share system connecting uni campus to metro	physical environment	cycling	Palma de Mallorca	Spain	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/public-bicycle-service-university-campus-palma-de-mallorca-spain	Adapted bike share to local circumstances	no info	no info	Not level of expected results - some theories to why		Yes
Bike to work campaign	social environment	cycling	nation wide	hungary	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/long-lasting-bike-work-campaign-hungary	adapted to local situation with website etc	no info	no info	yes	to some extent	Depended on EU financing...

Bike to work campaign	social environment	cycling	nation wide	Germany	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/bike-work-campaign-germany	set up is innovative / adapted to local circumstances	yes	yes	yes		yes
I love velo	Physical environment and social environment	cycling	5 cities	Romania	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/i-love-velo-romania-first-bike-sharing-scheme	new to Romania!	to some extent	yes		yes - in terms of number of users / rentals	yes
Walking maps to healthcare	social environment	walking	London	UK	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/encouraging-walking-hospitals-london-united-kingdom	new to this area	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes
Blue-bike: Belgium's national bicycle sharing	Physical environment and social environment	cycling	nation wide	Belgium	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/blue-bike-belgiums-national-bicycle-sharing-system	copied from OV-fiets	no	to some extent	yes	in terms of number of rentals	Yes

system	ment										
Hotel bike system	Physical environment and social environment	cycling	riccione	Italy	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/hotel-bike-system-riccione-italy	new to the town	no info	yes	no info	no	yes
Züriz'Fuess (Zürich on foot)	social environment	walking	Zurich	Switzerland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/zurich-towards-city-pedestrians-switzerland	new way to encourage people to walk - not sure how innovative this is	no	yes	yes	no	yes
Regional cycling plan	Physical environment and	cycling	Andalucia	Spain	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/andalucias-framework-regional-cycling-plan-spain	new to this part of the world	yes	yes	yes - evaluated future positiv	no (not yet)	yes

	social environment								e impact s ex ante		
Sydney wayfinding system	Physical environment and social environment	walking	Sydney	Australia	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/sydneys-pioneering-system-accessible-pedestrian-signs-australia	consideration wide range of users / accessibility of wayfinding system	no info	yes	yes	no (not yet)	yes
Street panthers	social environment	walking	nation wide	Greece	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/street-panthers-action-greece	yes	no	no - grassroots movement	yes	no	yes
Encouraging school children to keep cycling	social environment	cycling	Munich	Germany	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/encouraging-pupils-stay-their-bikes-munich-germany	yes	no info	yes	yes	yes	yes

Motivating residents to travel sustainability	social environment	walking and cycling	Helsinki	Finland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/motivating-residents-travel-sustainably-helsinki-finland	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes
Bike to work campaign	social environment	cycling	Gdynia	Poland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/promoting-cycling-new-employees-gdynia-poland	yes	no info	no info	yes	yes	yes
Active mobility day	social environment	walking and cycling	Ljubljana	Slovenia	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/raising-awareness-sustainable-mobility-ljubljana-slovenia	yes for this area - particularly institutional collaboration	no info	yes	yes	not in terms of increased levels AM	yes
Safer routes to school	social environment	walking and cycling	Skanderborg	Denmark	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/encouraging-cycling-and-walking-school-skanderborg-denmark	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes

Accessi- ble PT	Social environ- ment and physic- al environ- ment	walkin- g cyclin- g PT	Gothen- burg	Swede- n	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/improving-accessibility-transport-goteborg-sweden	yes	no info	yes	yes	yes	yes
PTP for cyclin- g	social environ- ment	cyclin- g	Riga	Latvia	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/public-events-personalised-travel-planning-riga-latvia	new to Riga	no info	yes	yes	no info	yes
workpla- ce MM	social enviorn- ment	walkin- g and cyclin- g	Dublin	Ireland	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/changing-mobility-choices-hospital-staff-dublin-ireland	new to site	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
integrat- ed planning	physic- al environ- ment, social environ- ment and legislati- on	walkin- g and cyclin- g	Houten	Nether- lands	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/promoting-traffic-safety-and-cycling-through-urban-design-houten-netherlands	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes

PTP for cycling	social environment	walking and cycling	LB Haringay	UK	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/personalised-travel-planning-boost-walking-and-cycling-haringey-uk	yes	sort of	yes	yes	yes	yes
Traffic parents	social environment	walking and cycling	Flanders Region	Belgium	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/traffic-parents-volunteers-professional-support-structure-belgium	yes	no info	yes	yes	no info	yes
Bicycle transport on PT	physical environment	cycling	Brno	Czech Republic	http://www.civitas.eu/content/extension-bicycle-transport-service-cycle-buses	yes	no info	yes	yes	no info - only pilot	yes
Public bike	physical environment	cycling	Malaga	Spain	http://www.civitas.eu/content/promotion-cycling-public-bicycle-scheme-malaga	yes to Malaga	no info	no info	yes	only in terms of users of bike sharing scheme	yes
Public bike	physical environment	cycling	Utrecht	Netherlands	http://www.civitas.eu/content/public-and-rental-bikes	aims different from most bike sharing scheme	no info	yes	not implemented due to change in politica		yes

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Superblocks	legislation / physical environment	cycling and walking	Donostia San Sebastian	Spain	http://www.civitas.eu/content/pedestrian-and-bicycle-lane-network	removal of car use	no info	yes	yes	yes	yes - used in Barcelona
Public transport priority	legislation / physical environment	public transport	Iasi	Romania	http://www.civitas.eu/content/bus-priority-measures	in this area	no info	yes	yes	yes	yes
Strolling zones	legislation / physical environment	walking	Graz	Austria	http://www.civitas.eu/content/introducing-strolling-zones	yes	no info	yes	yes	yes	yes
High quality bus lanes	physical environment	public transport	Toulouse	France	http://www.civitas.eu/content/developing-high-quality-bus-corridors-and-safe-city-centre-lanes	yes	no info	no info	yes	yes	yes

30 km/h speed limits	legislation / physical environment	walking and cycling	Graz	Austria	http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/citywide-30-kmh-speed-limit-city-graz-austria	yes	no info	no info	yes	to some extent	yes
'New parents' campaign in health centres	social environment	walking and cycling	Gdynia	Poland	http://epomm.eu/maxeva/index.php?id=2&proj_id=117	yes	yes	yes		yes	yes
Health campaign	social environment	walking and cycling	LB Hounslow	UK	http://epomm.eu/maxeva/index.php?id=2&proj_id=238	yes	yes	yes		yes	yes
Walking bus	social environment	walking	sofia	Bulgaria	http://epomm.eu/maxeva/index.php?id=2&proj_id=258	yes	to some extent	to some extent		yes	yes
Sustainable travel towns	all	all	3 cities	UK	http://epomm.eu/maxeva/index.php?id=2&proj_id=89	yes	to some extent	yes		yes	yes

Annex PASTA Glossary

PASTA glossary, first two fields

Term	Description
Accessibility	This term refers to the proximity of activities, destinations, goods, and services (incl. public transport) and is a function of population density, land use mix and, when specifically talking about public transport, its availability and frequency.
Active commuting	Active commuting relates to physical activity undertaken as a means of transport to work or study location.
Active mobility	Regular physical activity undertaken as a means of transport. It includes travel by foot, bicycle and other vehicles which require physical effort to get moving. Use of public transport is also included in the definition as it often involves some walking or cycling to pick-up and from drop-off points. It does not include walking, cycling or other physical activity that is undertaken for recreation purposes.
AM Measure	An active mobility measure is an action undertaken in order to increase the level of active mobility (in a specified population). This ranges from changing urban infrastructure or introducing new policies to campaigns to change people's transport behaviour.
Best practice AM measure	In combination with being a good practice measure, a best practice measure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aims to address both (urban and transport) planning and (health) policy objectives. (The collection of measures should indicate which types of interventions are most effective and to what extent in promoting health-enhancing physical activity, changing travel behaviour and promoting active mobility. But selected measures should also meet the objectives of sectors involved, e.g. reduction of traffic congestion or improvement in air quality). Is product of institutional co-operation. Collaboration is defined as joint work with partners for special purpose or endeavour or on a specific project. I.e. intersectorial collaboration and cross-sector collaboration (transport, environment, urban planning, land use, health administration, care and promotion, education, private, academic) in designing and implementing AM measures. Brings additional added value (social aspects, sustainability, health, economic added value). Has a high mainstream and transferability potential. Meets new challenges (demographic changes, environmental issues etc.) Have perceived considerable and measurable positive effects on AM and health. The measure is accompanied by an evaluation, possibly including measures of health outcomes, modal shifts and changes in levels of physical activity in the target groups.
Confounder	A variable that distorts the association between the exposure and the outcome, but is not an intervening causal variable (mediator).
Connectivity and permeability	These terms refer to the ease and directness of the movement of people and vehicles in a route network. Although these terms are sometimes used interchangeably, connectivity is sometimes used to refer solely to the number of connections, whereas the concept of permeability also includes the capacity of those connections.
Correlate	A variable that is associated or correlated with the outcome but its causality is not proven.
Cycling for leisure	Cycling during leisure time. It does not include cycling for transport.
Cycling for transport	Cycling undertaken as a means of transport from a place to another. (Can be dual purpose but MAIN purpose is means of transport). Travel individuals do to engage in activities in other places—work, recreation, shopping, health services: 'derived travel' (Krizek, 2009).
Determinant	A determinant is defined as a causal factor, and variation in this factor is followed systematically by variations in the outcome.

Exercise	Exercise is a subcategory of physical activity that is planned, structured and performed with the purpose of enhancing or maintaining one or more components of physical fitness.
Factor	A variable that is a correlate, determinant, confounder or a mediator.
Filtered permeability	A characteristic of a network that is more permeable to certain modes of transportation (in this case, walking and cycling) than others.
Good practice AM measure	A good practice AM measure is a successful measure. A good practice considered for PASTA is characterised by the following attributes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Includes an innovative approach beyond the common practice. (An innovative measure is one which exploits existing conditions to maximum effect in a new way). • The measure has led to an increase of AM; has been evaluated and/or measured; or has been perceived as successful.
Innovative AM measure	An innovative measure is one which exploits existing conditions to maximum effect in a new way.
Leisure time physical activity	Physical activity during leisure time. It does not include active mobility/active mobility.
Mediator	A variable on the causal pathway between exposure and outcome.
Middle-range theory	Theories that lie between the minor but necessary working hypotheses that evolve in abundance during day-to-day research and the all-inclusive systematic efforts to develop a unified theory. In realistic evaluation, this idea is applied in terms of developing a range of testable specific propositions (families of related context, mechanism, and outcome configurations) based on a small core of more abstract analytical frameworks.
Mobility	The movement of people across space. A term used in human geography, coined by John Urry at Lancaster University. NOT social mobility, or physiological mobility.
Moderator	A variable that alters the strength or direction of the relationship between the exposure and the outcome.
Physical activity	Any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that results in increased energy expenditure.
Pioneering cities	Pioneering cities/regions are addressing health issues in land use and transport planning with innovative thinking. Traditional actions to make streets greener, safer and more inviting to pedestrians, cyclists and public transport users are combined with suitable and supportive policy frameworks to increase the level of physical activity and replace car trips with active travel.
Policy	(a) A document that contains strategies and priorities, defines goals and objectives and is usually issued by a part of the administration. It is not unusual for other terms such as "action plan" or "strategy" being used for policies (b) a type of measure.
Programme	A set of measures or a single but large scale, long term activity which may or may not be related to a policy document. A programme can contain different types of activities, such as campaigns, events, specific offers or interventions and can be term limited or open ended.
Realistic evaluation	An approach (originally developed for the evaluation of social programs) that recognizes that the effect of interventions will vary according to the circumstances in which they are applied and therefore asks "why these interventions are (or are not) effective, in what ways, for whom and in what circumstances." It involves developing theories about how particular patterns of outcomes may be produced by particular causal mechanisms being triggered in particular contexts (so-called context, mechanism, and outcome configurations) and testing these theories cumulatively across different instances of the interventions/projects/policies.
Socio-ecological model	A model considering a variety of factors affecting an individual's physical activity behaviour. The factors can include the individual, the social environment, the physical environment and policies and regulations.
Successful active mobility measure	A measure with proven results on active mobility outcomes. Success (i.e. whether a measure 'worked' or 'did not work') of a measure may not easily be transferable because it is unique in term of its content (the detail of the measure/project) and its context (the social, community, and topographical environment). Success should also specify why a measure is (or is not) effective, in what ways, for whom, and in what circumstances.

Theory of planned behaviour	In psychology, the theory of planned behaviour is a theory about the link between beliefs and behaviour. The concept was proposed by Icek Ajzen to improve on the predictive power of the theory of reasoned action by including perceived behavioural control. It is one of the most predictive persuasion theories. It has been applied to studies of the relations among beliefs, attitudes, behavioural intentions and behaviours in various fields such as advertising, public relations, advertising campaigns and healthcare. The theory states that attitude toward behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, together shape an individual's behavioural intentions and behaviours.
Transport	Transport refers not only to infrastructure and its use but also the financial, administrative, legal, economic, social and cultural systems which underlie the development and use of the infrastructure.
Walking for leisure	Walking during leisure time. It does not include walking for transport.
Walking for transport	Walking undertaken as a means of transport from one place to another. (Can be dual purpose but MAIN purpose is means of transport). Travel individuals do to engage in activities in other places—work, recreation, shopping, health services: 'derived travel' (Krizek, 2009).